

**Learning from Safer Chemicals
for Safe-by-Design?**

This report makes suggestions for the further fleshing out of Safe-by-Design based on a brief exploration of initiatives from the realm of safer chemicals.

Client

The Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)

Contact person: Bart Walhout.

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Author

Dr Daan Schuurbiers

De Proeffabriek

Josef Israelslaan 63
6813 JB Arnhem
t: +31 6 143 652 16
e: daan@proeffabriek.nl
w: www.proeffabriek.nl

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Summary

This report makes suggestions for Safe-by-Design based on a brief exploration of initiatives from the world of safer chemicals. Safe-by-Design is an emerging policy movement that is focused on including safety, in the form of design requirements, as early as possible in product and process development in order to prevent potential risks to people and the environment.

Although the focus on Safe-by-Design is a fairly recent phenomenon, the broader ambition to take safety into account in chemical innovation has a longer history. How is Safe-by-Design related to more established concepts such as substitution, green chemistry, inherently safer technology, and circular economy? The goal of this brief study was to further explore one of these concepts, namely safer chemicals. What kinds of initiatives exist in the area of safer chemicals? Which actors are involved and how? What is the motivation for these initiatives? And to what extent are the goals being realised?

Varying practices

Due to increasing concerns about the potentially harmful effects of chemical substances on people and the environment, innumerable initiatives have been implemented since the 1980s that are focused on the safety of chemical substances. The term 'safer chemicals' refers to various practices within the context of this broad-based movement and includes initiatives for:

1. safer **use** of chemical substances. These initiatives primarily involve reducing the exposure to hazardous substances on the shop floor or in daily life, such as chemHAT¹ or the GoodGuide.²
2. safer **management** of chemical substances. Examples include safety measures with regard to storage and transport, reducing emissions, or improving process efficiency, as in the Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management.³
3. **substitution**, in the US better known as alternatives assessment: the replacement of chemical substances in production processes by safer alternatives. This includes initiatives such as the GreenScreen[®]⁴ or the OECD Substitution and Alternatives Assessment Toolbox.⁵
4. the **design** of safer chemical substances, whereby the integration of toxicology and chemistry into the design approach should lead to chemical alternatives with the same efficiency but lower toxicity. The Green Chemistry Institute of the American Chemical Society⁶ can serve as an example.

¹ www.chemhat.org

² www.goodguide.com

³ www.saicm.org

⁴ www.greenscreenchemicals.org

⁵ www.oecd-saatoobox.org

⁶ www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/about.html

Three overarching themes

Three dominant overarching themes were identified in exploring these initiatives:

1. **Knowledge development.** Safer use, management, production, and design of chemical substances requires knowledge of the physicochemical and structural properties of chemical substances as well as their toxicity or ecological toxicity, persistence, bioactive properties, degree and manner of use, exposure pathways, and behaviour in the environment. The necessary information on the properties of chemical substances is being developed, correlated, and made available in innumerable initiatives all over the world.
2. **Collaboration.** Dealing with chemical substances more safely also requires new forms of collaboration between risk researchers, developers, producers, downstream users, government, and civil society. This collaboration is implemented in three ways:
 1. The *practical guidance* provided to producers and developers by risk researchers on how to deal with chemical substances more safely;
 2. *Collaborative design* of new chemical substances by chemists, toxicologists, and product developers;
 3. *Stakeholder consultations* with regard to regulations for chemical safety.
3. **Social responsibility.** Based on the conviction that the chemical industry plays a leading role in opting for the safer use, management, production, and design of chemical substances, various initiatives on safer chemicals attempt to create a greater level of safety awareness within the business sector via self-regulation or pressure from external sources.

Learning from safer chemicals for Safe-by-Design?

- The central concept underlying Safe-by-Design, namely taking safety considerations into account from the first stage of development, sounds simple enough. However, the exploration of the safer chemicals theme makes it clear how complicated it is to realise this self-evident concept in practice. To make a well-considered choice for an alternative that has proven to be safer, it is necessary to first connect a very diverse set of data on an ever-growing collection of chemical substances. The challenge for Safe-by-Design is even greater, as this concept includes nanotechnology and biotechnology in addition to chemical substances.
- The practical application of safety considerations is not simply a question of *developing* information, but also of effectively *transferring* this information to the user. This requires risk researchers to take on a guiding and advisory role. The suggestion for Safe-by-Design is not to develop knowledge via a top-down approach, from the traditional risk research perspective, but to do so in collaboration with the intended user and within the context of the application: in what *form* does the knowledge already available have to be presented to the diverse target groups so that the knowledge provided actually meets the needs of the user for more knowledge? What kind of *guidance* do developers, producers, and consumers need to actually take considerations of safety into account in the design phase?

- The exploration of safer chemicals shows that new forms of collaboration offer opportunities, but can also lead to tensions between the new and traditional roles of stakeholders. Which forms of collaboration are advocated by Safe-by-Design? Who works with whom in which phases of research and innovation, and in which role? And what are the potential consequences of this collaboration for the roles and responsibilities of stakeholders?
- A guiding normative ideal can help in motivating target groups, but an appeal to morality is not in itself sufficient to lead to a change in direction with regard to the safer use of chemical substances. In addition to self-regulation, compliance monitoring remains necessary. In other words, prevention cannot completely replace management.

These considerations indicate why it is so difficult to reach agreement on apparently simple questions such as, 'What is Safe-by-Design?' The further implementation of Safe-by-Design is not only a question of formulating a new design approach focused on safety. By definition, it also requires policy choices regarding the role of government in relation to the business sector and civil society as well as the desired balance between precautionary measures and innovation.

1. Introduction

This report makes suggestions for Safe-by-Design based on a brief exploration of initiatives from the world of safer chemicals. Safe-by-Design is an emerging policy movement that is focused on including safety, in the form of design requirements, as early as possible in product and process development in order to prevent potential risks to people and the environment. Although the focus on Safe-by-Design is a fairly recent phenomenon, the broader ambition to take safety into account in chemical innovation has a longer history. How is Safe-by-Design related to more established concepts such as substitution, green chemistry, inherently safer technology, and circular economy? Figure 1 illustrates the concepts often mentioned in relation to Safe-by-Design.

Figure 1: Positioning of Safe-by-Design relative to related concepts.

In order to be able to “place” them within the overall context, these concepts are positioned along two axes. The horizontal axis indicates the degree to which the concept primarily focuses on ‘substances’ (research & development and production of chemical substances) or on ‘processes’ ((how to deal with substances). The vertical axis indicates the degree to which the concept deals more with ‘safety’ (preventing damage to health) or more with ‘sustainability’ (satisfying the needs of the present generation without endangering the needs of future generations, here as well as in other parts of the world)⁷ as a guiding principle. For example, circular design is focused more strongly on *sustainability* than on safety, and it deals more with *process design* and less with substance design (thereby placing it in the lower right hand quadrant). In contrast, safer chemicals focuses on the *safety of chemical substances* (and therefore ends up in the upper left quadrant).

As the concept itself of Safe-by-Design is still being developed, the positioning relative to these concepts may still undergo some changes (this is also true, in a certain sense, of all the

⁷ This is the definition of sustainability from the 1987 Brundlandt report ‘Our Common Future’: <http://www.un-documents.net/our-common-future.pdf>.

concepts in the figure).⁸ The insights gained from these domains can serve as a source of inspiration for the further implementation of Safe-by-Design. Although previous experiences cannot be extrapolated to the present on a one-on-one basis, it is also true that encouraging examples, common pitfalls, and underlying structural similarities from the past can serve as relevant background information. However, assuming that all the differing points of departure from all these movements cannot be integrated into a single concept, we may have to make certain *choices*: Is Safe-by-Design primarily concerned with safety or also with sustainability? Does it deal primarily with substances or also with processes? With which of these neighbouring domains, does Safe-by-Design have the most overlap?

Goal and approach of the exploration

The goal of this exploration of the ‘world of safer chemicals’ is therefore to find relevant information from the world of safer chemicals for the positioning of Safe-by-Design. What kinds of initiatives exist in the area of safer chemicals? Which actors are involved and how? What is the motivation for these initiatives? To what extent are the goals being realised? What obstacles are being encountered? And to what extent can these experiences help in strengthening Safe-by-Design as an emerging policy movement? The primary focus in this regard was on exploring initiatives in the area of substance safety. Although an exploration of initiatives dealing with process safety, for example within the rich tradition of Inherently Safer Technology, would also be relevant for Safe-by-Design, it is beyond the scope of this brief exploration.

The concept of ‘safer chemicals’ was initially explored within its full range by simply reviewing the results provided by online search engines for the term ‘safer chemicals’. A search of relevant websites provided an overview of initiatives in this area. A further examination of these initiatives led, in turn, to other initiatives and publications in the ‘grey’ as well as scientific literature. This exploration does not claim to provide an exhaustive analysis of all initiatives in the field of safer chemicals. It is quite possible that this ‘snowball method’ did not capture all initiatives. However, a certain degree of saturation became apparent at the end of the exploration: the most striking initiatives were being repeatedly identified, and the number of newly discovered initiatives continued to decline. The study took place from August 2018 to March 2019.

Structure of this report

The following chapter first sketches the landscape of initiatives in the world of safer chemicals and discusses the various meanings attached to the concept. The exploration of the landscape revealed three overarching themes: knowledge development, collaboration, and social responsibility. Chapters 3, 4, and 5 discuss these three themes consecutively and explore possible clues for the positioning of Safe-by-Design.

⁸ It is conceivable that these concepts have actually taken root *because* they can be interpreted in various ways. For more information, also see a previous study that is part of the broader environmental analysis of Safe-by-Design, [‘Learning from Green Chemistry for Safe-by-Design’](#).

Who is involved?

There are various types of initiators:

- (Partnerships between) national and regional governments such as the Interstate Chemicals Clearinghouse (IC2),¹⁰ the Washington State Department of Ecology,¹¹ and the International Sustainable Chemistry Collaborative Centre (ISC3),¹²
- International government organisations such as the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP),
- Environmental agencies such as the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) in Europe and the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in the US.
- Research institutes and associations such as The Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM),¹³ TNO,¹⁴ the Massachusetts Toxics Use Reduction Institute (TURI)¹⁵ and the Green Chemistry Institute of the American Chemical Society (ACS-GCI).¹⁶
- (Associations of) the chemical industry, such as the International Council of Chemical Associations (ICCA),¹⁷ the European Chemical Industry Council (CEFIC)¹⁸ and the Association of the Dutch Chemical Industry (VNCI).¹⁹
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) such as the International Persistent Organic Pollutants Elimination Network (IPEN),²⁰ ChemSec (the International Chemical Secretariat) in Sweden,²¹ Safer Chemicals, Healthy Families,²² Health Care Without Harm,²³ the Alliance of Nurses for Healthy Environments (ANHE)²⁴ and Clean Production Action in the US.²⁵

What do they do?

The initiatives themselves vary in nature: the term ‘safer chemicals’ can refer to:

1. safer *use* of chemical substances. These initiatives primarily involve reducing the exposure to hazardous substances on the shop floor or in daily life. For example, the Chemical Hazard and Alternatives Toolbox (ChemHAT)²⁶ provides information on the use of hazardous

¹⁰ <http://theic2.org/>

¹¹ <https://ecology.wa.gov/>

¹² <https://www.isc3.org>

¹³ <https://www.rivm.nl/>

¹⁴ <https://www.tno.nl>

¹⁵ <https://www.turi.org/>

¹⁶ <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/about.html>

¹⁷ <https://www.icca-chem.org/>

¹⁸ <http://www.cefic.org/>

¹⁹ <https://www.vnci.nl/>

²⁰ <https://ipen.org/>

²¹ <https://chemsec.org/>

²² <https://saferchemicals.org/who-we-are/>

²³ <https://noharm-global.org/>

²⁴ <https://envirn.org/>

²⁵ <https://www.cleanproduction.org/>

²⁶ <http://www.chemhat.org>

substances on the shop floor. The GoodGuide²⁷ and the Safer Choice programme²⁸ of the EPA inform consumers about hazardous substances in products and provide safer alternatives when possible.

2. safer *management* of chemical substances. Examples include safety measures for storage and transport as well as measures aimed at reducing emissions or improving process efficiency. For example, the Responsible Care programme, a voluntary initiative of the chemical industry, focuses primarily on the safer use and management of chemical substances in industrial production²⁹ The Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management (SAICM), a large-scale initiative of the United Nation's Environment Programme (UNEP), focuses primarily on the responsible management of chemical substances.
3. *substitution*, in the US better known as *alternatives assessment*: the replacement of chemical substances in production processes by safer alternatives. For example, the GreenScreen for Safer Chemicals® helps companies to identify problematic substances and to replace them with safer alternatives.³⁰ And ChemSec (The International Chemical Secretariat, a Swedish NGO that aims to free the world from hazardous chemical substances) has drafted the SIN List, a searchable list of 919 hazardous substances that are expected to become banned or limited.³¹ The idea here is that companies can consult the list before choosing a specific chemical substance for a production process.
4. the *design* of new and safer chemical alternatives. The primary goal here is to integrate toxicology and chemistry into the design of *inherently* safe chemistry. After all, a better understanding of the physicochemical causes of the toxicity of chemical substances can lead to chemical alternatives with the same efficiency but lower toxicity. This is what is meant by the concept, for example, according to the Green Chemistry Institute of the American Chemical Society.³² The Safe Chemicals Innovation Agenda (SCIA),³³ a collective initiative of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate in the Netherlands, also assigns an important role to research and development. The SCIA identifies seven research priorities for safer chemical substances, materials, and products. These include alternatives for fluorinated chemicals in cleaning agents, less toxic flame retardants, and substitutes for volatile organic compounds in solvents.

An exploration of the world of safer chemicals is therefore an exploration of various, partially overlapping worlds (see Figure 3). The term 'safer chemicals' includes initiatives in the areas of personal safety, process safety, substitution, and chemical innovation.

²⁷ <https://www.goodguide.com>

²⁸ <https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice>

²⁹ <https://www.icca-chem.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/Responsible-Care-Global-Charter-Guide.pdf>

³⁰ <https://www.greenscreenchemicals.org/>

³¹ <https://chemsec.org/sin-list/>

³² <https://www.acs.org/content/acs/en/greenchemistry/principles.html>

³³ <https://www.chemischestoffenogedgergeld.nl/sites/default/files/39982%20-%20Safe%20Chemicals%20Innovation%20Agenda%20-%2020180613i6%20final%20copy.pdf>

Figure 3: The term 'safer chemicals' refers to diverse initiatives ranging from managing to preventing the harmful effects of chemical substances.

What is noticeable?

1. Overlap and differences with green chemistry

The initiatives in the field of safer chemicals that focus on the design aspects have clear areas of overlap with green chemistry.³⁴ The basic premise of green chemistry is to design chemical products and processes in such a manner that the production and emission of hazardous substances is reduced or even completely prevented. Safety clearly plays a role in green chemistry. At least four of the twelve principles are focused on safety (including principles #3: *Design less hazardous chemical synthesis*; #4: *Design safer chemicals and products*; #5: *Use safer solvents and reaction conditions*; and #12: *Minimize the potential for accidents*)³⁵, although it is debatable to what extent this theoretical focus is also reflected in the practical implementation of the concept. Conversely, the goals of many initiatives from the world of safer chemicals show similarities with the basic premise of green chemistry, such as the BizNGO Principles for Safer Chemicals: '*Redesign products and processes to avoid the use and/or generation of hazardous chemicals.*' Initiatives from the world of safer chemicals are frequently focused not only on safety but also on sustainability.

However, in spite of the overlap between both concepts, there are also clear differences in emphasis. Initiatives from the world of 'safer chemicals' seem to have a more practical focus than those from green chemistry. Green chemistry is based on a positive philosophy of making the world a better place via intelligent chemical design. Due to this design approach, initiatives from green chemistry seem to primarily attract actors at the beginning of the innovation

³⁴ By the way, this also applies to the concepts of green chemistry and substitution in relation to each other. Many of the success stories attributed to the green chemistry movement, such as the often-quoted *Green Journey* of Pfizer, which put green chemistry on the map for the pharmaceutical industry, are often examples of 'traditional' substitution.

³⁵ Also see the report of the previous study into green chemistry for more details about the twelve principles: <http://proeffabriek.nl/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/Learning-from-Green-Chemistry-for-Safe-by-Design-DPF-2018-in-Dutch.pdf>

pipeline, such as researchers and innovative companies. The emphasis here is on the development of new chemical products and processes (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Areas of overlap and differences between green chemistry and safer chemicals

Initiatives from the world of safer chemicals often play a role later on in the innovation pipeline. These initiatives focus more on practical results, such as reducing exposure or replacing substances of very high concern by safer alternatives. However, the above does not mean per se that the impact of safer chemicals is smaller. As the downstream volumes are much larger, the successful replacement of a chemical substance can have a major impact.

2. Overarching themes

Three dominant overarching themes were identified in exploring the broad collection of initiatives from the world of safer chemicals.

1. **Knowledge development** Safer use, management, production, and design of chemical substances requires knowledge of the physicochemical and structural properties of chemical substances as well as their toxicity or ecological toxicity, persistence, bioactive properties, degree and manner of use, exposure pathways, and behaviour in the environment. The necessary information on the properties of chemical substances is being developed, correlated, and made available in innumerable initiatives all over the world.
2. **Collaboration.** Dealing with chemical substances more safely also requires new forms of collaboration between risk researchers, developers, producers, downstream users, government, and civil society. This collaboration is implemented in three ways:
 1. The *practical guidance* provided to producers and developers by risk researchers on how to deal with chemical substances more safely;
 2. *Collaborative design* of new chemical substances by chemists, toxicologists, and product developers;
 3. *Stakeholder consultations* with regard to regulations for chemical safety.
3. **Social responsibility.** Based on the conviction that the chemical industry plays a leading role in opting for a safer use, management, production, and design of chemical substances, various safer chemical initiatives attempt to create a greater level of safety

awareness within the business sector via self-regulation (such as Responsible Care) or via pressure by external sources (such as Safer Made, an investment fund that invests in safer products and technologies).³⁶

The next chapters delve more deeply into these overarching themes. As the same themes also play a major role in the discussion of Safe-by-Design, we will explore, for each theme, what lessons can be learned from these experiences from the world of safer chemicals that are also relevant for the further implementation of Safe-by-Design.

³⁶ <https://www.safermade.net/>

3. Knowledge development

The main focus of most of the initiatives from the world of safer chemicals is on developing and making available knowledge about the risks of chemical substances. The exploration uncovered what was, at first sight, a dizzying quantity of information on chemical substances. All this information is based on a wide collection of data sources for a variety of target groups, in which the various properties of chemical substances are set down. There are databanks that characterise, classify, and label chemical substances on the basis of their physicochemical and structural properties, such as ChemSpider, ZINC15 or eChemPortal (see Table 1 for an overview of data sources). Other databanks, such as TOXNET, ECOTOX or RISCTOX, collect the results of risk research, including data on toxicity, eco-toxicity, bio-active properties, and the behaviour of substances in the environment. Then there are also databanks that collect information on exposure data and limit values for using substances on the shop floor, such as the OSHA Occupational Chemical Database or Haz-Map.

Table 1: A sampling of the available data sources on safer chemicals.

Instrument	Description	Web link
ChemSpider	Information on the chemical structure of more than 71 million structures from hundreds of data sources.	http://www.chemspider.com/
ChemView	Chemical safety data collected by the United States EPA on the basis of the Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA).	https://chemview.epa.gov/
eChemPortal	Information collected by the OECD on physicochemical properties, toxicity or eco-toxicity, and exposure data for hundreds of thousands of substances from dozens of data sources.	https://www.echemportal.org/
ECOTOX	Collected eco-toxicity data from the EPA, on the effects of more than 10,000 substances on 12,000 species.	https://cfpub.epa.gov/ecotox/
Haz-Map	Information from the United States National Institutes of Health on the health effects of substances used on the shop floor, intended for occupational health & safety professionals and consumers.	https://hazmap.nlm.nih.gov/
OSHA Occupational Chemical Database	Information on properties and exposure limits of substances used on the shop floor, from the United States Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA)	https://www.osha.gov/chemicaldata/
RISCTOX	Risk information on more than 100,000 chemical substances from the Spanish ISTAS in collaboration with ETUI and the EEB.	http://risctox.istas.net/en/
TOXNET	A collection of databases from the United States National Institutes of Health, with data on hundreds of thousands of potentially hazardous substances.	https://toxnet.nlm.nih.gov/
Safer Chemical Ingredients List (SCIL)	A list of substances that comply with the strict safety requirements of the Safer Choice programme of the EPA	https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice/safer-ingredients#scil
The SIN list	A list of 919 hazardous substances that have been designated by the Swedish ChemSec organisation as Substances of Very High Concern.	http://sinlist.chemsec.org/
ZINC15	Information on the properties of 230 million commercially available compounds.	http://zinc15.docking.org/

In addition to these detailed sources of research information, there are also lists with information on commonly used substances for downstream users in specific sectors such as

the textile, electronics, and cleaning agent industries, as well as lists of banned substances or substances of concern such as the SIN List. Finally, there are lists with the composition of consumer products such as the Safer Chemical Ingredients List, intended to enable consumers to choose safer products. It should be noted that the above is only a small sampling of the enormous quantity of information available.

Instruments

Building further on this broad base of data sources, a wide range of instruments have also been developed to make it easier for various target groups to actually use the information (see Table 2). These instruments range from portals, in which various databases are collected, to detailed handbooks for determining safer alternatives. For example, the OECD Substitution and Alternatives Assessment Toolbox provides access to a broad collection of information sources on the properties of chemical substances, handbooks for determining safer alternatives, case studies, and information on the regulations and restrictions that apply to chemical substances worldwide (also see Appendix A for more information on the OECD SAAT Toolbox).

Table 2: Some instruments and portals that aim to make information on chemical substances more user-friendly

Instrument	Description	Web link
Design for the Environment Alternatives Assessments	An overview of alternative assessments by the EPA that identify safer alternatives for commonly used substances such as bisphenol A, flame retardants, and nonylphenol ethoxylates.	https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice/design-environment-alternatives-assessments
GoodGuide	The GoodGuide assigns a score to consumer products based on the safety of the ingredients used.	https://www.goodguide.com
GreenScreen® for Safer Chemicals	A method developed by Clean Production Action to assess chemical risks and thereby to identify substances of concern and generate safer alternatives.	http://www.greenscreenchemicals.org
IC2 Alternatives Assessment Guide	A handbook from the Interstate Chemicals Clearinghouse that helps producers replace hazardous substances with safer alternatives.	http://theic2.org/article/download-pdf/file_name/IC2_AA_Guide_Version_1.1.pdf
IOMC Toolbox	An instrument from the Inter-Organization Programme for the Sound Management of Chemicals (IOMC) that helps countries manage chemical substances.	http://ocde.preprod.agence-modedemploi.fr/integration/?page=homepage
Kemi PRIO	An instrument from the Swedish Kemi that helps producers to identify safer alternatives for various substances of concern.	https://www.kemi.se/en/prio-start
OECD Substitution and Alternatives Assessment Toolbox	A broad collection of sources and instruments in the area of substitution and alternatives assessment, put together by the OECD.	http://www.oecd-saatoolbox.org
Pollution Prevention Options Analysis System: (P2OASys)	An instrument from the Toxics Use Reduction Institute (TURI) that helps companies in determining the health and environmental effects of chemical alternatives.	https://p2oasys.turi.org/
Quick Chemical Assessment Tool (QCAT)	A simplified version of the GreenScreen®, developed by the Department of Ecology of Washington State in the US that enables smaller companies to quickly find chemical alternatives.	https://ecology.wa.gov/Regulations-Permits/Guidance-technical-assistance/Preventing-hazardous-waste-pollution/Safer-alternatives/Quick-tool-for-assessing-chemicals
The Substitution Support Portal (SUBSPORT)	A collection of information sources on substitution, including lists of hazardous substances, substitution handbooks, case studies, and trainings.	https://www.subsport.eu/

Many of these instruments have a long history. In the 1990s, the EPA already developed the Design for the Environment (DfE) programme.³⁷ This programme developed a series of risk indicators for identifying potential substitutes for substances of high concern. The EPA worked together with producers on a DfE label for consumer products. This programme was later renamed Safer Choice.³⁸ Products are awarded a Safer Choice label if they minimise the harmful effects on people and the environment. The Safer Chemical Ingredient List (SCIL), with information on the safety of chemical substances in consumer products, is also a product of the Safer Choice programme.³⁹

The DfE programme also provided the basis for the GreenScreen® for Safer Chemicals, developed by Clean Production Action. GreenScreen® is an instrument used to assess chemical risks and thereby to identify substances of concern and generate safer alternatives. The instrument was developed in 2007 and is used by companies, governments, and NGOs to facilitate product design and development, to purchase raw materials and other materials, and to carry out alternatives assessments (legally required or voluntary).

GreenScreen® builds further on the 12 principles of green chemistry and the DfE alternatives assessment method. It presents the available data on the inherent properties of a substance, such as toxicity and health and environmental effects, in a risk table. This risk assessment results in a benchmark that enables a simple comparison between various substances: 1) Avoid – Chemical of High concern; 2) Use but Search for Safer Substitute; 3) Use but Still Opportunity for Improvement; 4) Prefer – Safer Chemical. GreenScreen® therefore allows companies to sort substances in terms of preference. This method is used by companies such as Walmart, Hewlett Packard (HP), Levi Strauss & Co, and Apple.

However, as GreenScreen® requires extensive expertise and significant investments in time and money, it is not suitable for smaller companies. The Department of Ecology of the State of Washington in the US therefore developed the Quick Chemical Assessment Tool (QCAT), a simplified version of GreenScreen®. QCAT enables smaller companies to quickly find chemical alternatives. However, as QCAT is much less extensive, there is a greater risk of ‘regrettable substitutions’, the replacement of one harmful substance by another.

Knowledge development: challenges

Unlocking the knowledge available on the safe use, management, and design of chemicals is a formidable challenge. In the first place, it’s already quite a challenge to include the enormous quantity of information available on chemical substances in a single overview. After all, this involves millions of disparate data entries on hundreds of thousands of compounds and substances from hundreds of databanks all over the world. In order to make an objective choice for safer alternatives and to reduce the likelihood of regrettable substitutions, these very diverse data must first be connected and compared to each other. This requires a generally accepted framework for comparison, and also assumes that producers and researchers are willing to generate and share the data and that the quality of the data used is satisfactory. In recent years, a great deal of attention has therefore also been focused on the

³⁷ This information comes from the Quick Chemical Assessment Tool Version 2.0 of the Washington State Department of Ecology: <https://fortress.wa.gov/ecy/publications/documents/1404033.pdf>.

³⁸ <https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice>

³⁹ <https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice/safer-ingredients>

application of the FAIR principles. These are intended to ensure that data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. However, out of concern that sensitive business information will be released, companies are not always willing to disclose their in-house knowledge.

In addition, the fields of research involved in collecting safety data are themselves also subject to continuous development. There is therefore a risk of databanks becoming outdated, measurement methods being modified, or data being interpreted differently. The instruments used therefore need to be continually modified on the basis of new insights.⁴⁰

Moreover, the list of new chemical substances being produced is continually growing. According to the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, a new chemical substance sees the light of day every 2.6 seconds.⁴¹ The most important properties of these substances (physicochemical properties, toxicity or eco-toxicity, exposure routes, behaviour in the environment, et cetera) would also have to be determined and shared in order to allow for a proper comparison with existing substances. However, for most of these new substances, insufficient information is available on chemical characteristics to make such a comparison possible. This immediately raises the question of how to deal with what we do not yet know. Predictions with regard to new chemical substances can be made only on the basis of the structural properties of the substance. Sometimes a comparison can be made with known structures in order to make a prediction of the expected properties of the substance. This leads to the grouping of chemical substances (see OECD, 2014). The less knowledge there is on the properties of the substance, the more variables there are that influence the choice of an alternative, so that a choice then needs to be made on the basis of *expected* properties.

In brief, choices for safer alternatives are made within a context of uncertainty. In some cases, there is so much information available on the properties and use of a substance that the alternative can be considered as being proven to be safer, but in many cases the choice is much less evident. In addition, the safety of a chemical substance is determined not only by its inherent physicochemical properties but also by the extent and manner of its use. In other words, the data sources and instruments that are intended to unlock the knowledge available on the safe use, management, and design of substances do not provide an answer on their own. The choice of a safer alternative is also influenced by the specific context of its use.

However, this context is very variable. The potential users of this information are an extremely diverse group, ranging from chemical giants to small producers and consumers. It is no simple matter to serve all these groups effectively and efficiently. What level of background knowledge can we assume to be present? Even the simplest instruments in the overview presented above require a solid background of chemical knowledge. Larger companies can perhaps afford the investments needed for the careful management of chemical substances on the shop floor, but smaller companies are less likely to be able to do so.

Initiatives in the area of safer chemicals are therefore increasingly focusing on new forms of collaboration between knowledge providers (chemists, toxicologists, biologists, materials scientists, occupational hygienists, regulatory agencies, etc.) and users (developers, producers,

⁴⁰ The ACS Green Chemistry Institute, in its White Paper *Green Nanotechnology Challenges And Opportunities* (2011), comes to the same conclusion: 'Toxicology and analysis protocols need to be developed and constantly updated to reflect advances in the science.' See: https://greennano.org/sites/greennano2.uoregon.edu/files/GCI_WP_GN10.pdf

⁴¹ Ellen MacArthur Foundation: The role of Safe Chemistry and Healthy Materials in Unlocking the Circular Economy: <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/assets/downloads/The-Role-of-Safe-Chemistry-and-Healthy-Materials-in-Unlocking-the-Circular-Economy.pdf>

and consumers). These initiatives aim to empower and motivate the intended user to apply the available knowledge in practice. The following chapter delves more deeply into the various forms of collaboration being developed to encourage working with chemical substances more safely.

'Lessons' for Safe-by-Design?

These considerations indicate how complicated it is to actually realise the central concept underlying Safe-by-Design in practice, namely including safety as early as possible as a design criterion in product and process development. Acquiring and making available the necessary information is already an enormous challenge in relation to the chemical substances themselves, in view of the quantity and diversity of this data. But in addition, the data sources and tools providing knowledge on the safer use, management, and design of chemical substances only acquire real meaning within the specific context of use.

A possible lesson to be learned for Safe-by-Design from this exploration is that risk researchers need to provide support and advice for the practical implementation of safety considerations. New initiatives should not be developed in a top-down manner, from a traditional risk research perspective, but rather in collaboration with the intended user and within the specific context of the application: in what *form* should the knowledge already available be presented so that it can actually be used for the design of safer chemical substances? What kind of guidance do developers, producers, and users need in order to actually include safety considerations in the design phase?

However, the challenge for Safe-by-Design is even greater, as this concept includes nanotechnology and biotechnology in addition to chemical substances. As chemical substances, nanotechnology, and biotechnology all involve different domains, with different stakeholders, different applications, and different policy and regulatory frameworks, the information required and the kind of guidance needed will differ for each area of application. The process of determining safer alternatives turns out to be an even bigger challenge when it comes to nanomaterials, as this often involves new compounds at levels of scale for which very little data is available. Determining the safer choice therefore has to take place on the basis of the expected properties of the material (the *risk potentials*). However, the actual effects of substances are also influenced by the degree and manner of use,⁴² and very little is known about this in the case of nanomaterials.

The same questions also play a role in three new EU projects, NANORIGO,⁴³ GOV4NANO⁴⁴ and RISKGONE⁴⁵, which were recently started within the context of the NMBP-13-2018 call for proposals on Risk Governance in Nanotechnology for the European Commission.⁴⁶ The challenge faced by these projects lies not so much in producing the knowledge required for risk assessment, but rather in defining a suitable design approach with which the various stakeholders can work together to effectively manage the risks of nanomaterials.

⁴² Also see the article on Safe-by-Design by Krom, Walhout and Klaassen (2019) in a special issue of NanoEthics.

⁴³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/220129/factsheet/en>

⁴⁴ <https://www.gov4nano.eu/>

⁴⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/220127/factsheet/en>

⁴⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/nmbp-13-2018>

4. Collaboration

Dealing with chemical substances more safely also requires new forms of collaboration between risk researchers, developers, producers, downstream users, government, and civil society. In the world of safer chemicals, this collaboration is implemented in three ways:

1. Practical guidance provided to producers and developers by risk researchers on how to deal with chemical substances more safely

As indicated in the previous chapter, attention is increasingly being focused on the practical guidance provided to producers by risk researchers. As the data sources and instruments for the safer use, management, and design of substances only provide added value within the context of use, various initiatives focus on providing training and advice to the intended users of these data sources, in order to translate the knowledge available into practical choices. For example, Clean Production Action offers training for professionals in applying the GreenScreen® method in their own company.⁴⁷ The Toxics Use Reduction Institute offers a certified training course to become a *Toxics Use Reduction Planner*, during which trainees learn how they can reduce the use of hazardous substances in their own work environment.⁴⁸ The goal is to ensure that the information already present is accessible, understandable, and applicable.

2. Collaborative design of new chemical substances by chemists, toxicologists, and product developers

There is a growing focus on closer research collaboration between toxicologists, chemists, and product developers for the *design* of safer chemical substances. This primarily involves collaboration between a wide range of disciplines in an early stage of the development process, so that the harmful effects of chemical substances are prevented early on in the design phase. This is very much in line with the philosophy of green chemistry. In an article in *Science*, titled 'Toward designing safer chemicals', Julie Zimmerman and Paul Anastas (2015) write: "*to design more benign products, processes, and systems, [...] one area perhaps requires primary focus: transdisciplinarity. Research institutes, universities, industry, and funding and regulatory agencies (among other stakeholders) must cultivate a research ecosystem in which efforts are collaborative and knowledge is shared across disciplines, including pharmacology, (eco)toxicology, chemistry, modeling, and biostatistics.*" The Safe Chemicals Innovation Agenda also emphasises the need for transdisciplinary collaboration for the development of safe materials and products.⁴⁹ The idea behind this is that inherently safe chemical substances will, once available, make control measures superfluous.

3. Stakeholder consultations with regard to regulations for chemical safety

There is a great deal of attention being paid to new forms of collaboration between the business sector, government, and civil society in relation to *regulations* dealing with chemical substances. The European Chemicals agency (ECHA) views coordination and collaboration

⁴⁷ <https://www.greenscreenchemicals.org/learn/training>

⁴⁸ https://www.turi.org/Our_Work/Training/Become_a_TUR_Planner_Certification_Course

⁴⁹ http://www.greenchemistryvienna2018.com/fileadmin/inhalte/gcc/pdf/Safe_Chemicals_Innovation_Agenda.pdf

among the many stakeholders as one of the focal areas of the new substitutionary strategy (ECHA, 2018): *“Collaborative networks for innovation and substitution can play an important role in coordinating and advancing the practice of informed substitution. They can also support innovation through the development, evaluation and adoption of safer alternatives.”* The same emphasis on collaborative relationships between government entities can also be found in SAICM and in the Global Chemicals Outlook. The UN Global compact, a voluntary multi-stakeholder initiative for implementing the UN sustainability principles, also emphasises the importance of collaboration between government entities, businesses, and NGOs.⁵⁰

Changing roles of stakeholders

These attempts to forge new forms of collaboration at various levels (practical guidance/coaching, design, and regulations) can be seen as the expression of a growing awareness that a safer approach towards chemical substances (and in particular the transition from a focus on managing the harmful effects of chemical substances towards the prevention of these effects) requires changes in the roles of the parties involved.

For example, the role of NGOs in the intended collaborative frameworks changes from a role as outsiders to a role as collaborative partners. SustainAbility, a sustainability consultancy, already described the changing role of NGOs in 2003 in ‘the 21st Century NGO’. According to this report, NGOs in the 20th century operated primarily as outsiders who criticised the system from the outside. They were focused primarily on identifying problems, and their message was primarily viewed as the expression of public dissatisfaction. In the 21st century, NGOs position themselves more often as partners, focusing primarily on searching for constructive solutions with added value for the target group. Although this characterisation is not 100% correct, the transition from traditional roles to newer ones is reflected in the role played by organisations such as ChemSec and IPEN within the framework of large-scale initiatives such as SAICM. NGOs such as The Nature Conservancy⁵¹ and the Environmental Defence Fund (EDF) also position themselves primarily as partners.⁵² For example, the EDF worked closely together with DuPont on the development of a risk assessment framework for nanomaterials (see Krabbenborg, 2013).

The emphasis on partnership is also reflected in the changing roles of government entities and the business sector. For example, since the 1990s, as the focus has shifted from the management to the prevention of problems associated with chemical substances, the role of government has shifted from inspection and control to collaboration. A similar trend can be seen in how companies position themselves. There is an increasing focus on stakeholder involvement and on the social responsibility of companies (also see next chapter).

These changing roles are expressed in new initiatives such as BizNGO,⁵³ an initiative of Clean Production Action. BizNGO is a collaborative framework of companies, environmental organisations, government entities, and universities that is focused on the use of safer chemicals in the economy. Established in 2006, BizNGO works with companies from various sectors such as electronics, healthcare, retail, construction, and cleaning agents. Participating NGOs include Health Care Without Harm, Electronics Take Back Coalition, Healthy Building

⁵⁰ <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/>

⁵¹ <https://www.nature.org/en-us/>

⁵² <https://www.edf.org/>

⁵³ <https://www.bizngo.org/>

Network and the Investor Environmental Health Network. According to BizNGO, the dialogue between companies and NGOs helps in gaining a better understanding of the concerns regarding the health effects of chemical products on people and the environment and in identifying such problems at an earlier stage.

Collaboration: challenges

The potential benefits of better collaboration are clear: collaboration between risk researchers and producers facilitates the choice for the safer use, production, and management of chemical substances; transdisciplinary collaboration between researchers and developers can ensure that harmful effects are already reduced as much as possible in the research phase or even eliminated entirely; collaboration between producers, regulators, and NGOs can lead to regulations that are better aligned with the wishes and concerns of society.

However, in addition to the above opportunities, challenges also exist. New roles for stakeholders can conflict with traditional role assignments. For example, the reputation of NGOs as protectors of the public interest can become endangered as a result of excessively close collaboration with the business sector. The collaboration mentioned above between the EDF and DuPont in the formulation of a risk assessment framework for nanomaterials led to strong criticism. Critical NGOs such as Greenpeace, Friends of the Earth and the ETC group are opposed to: *'any process in which public participation in government oversight of nanotechnology policy is usurped by industry and its allies'* (Krabbenborg, 2013). Out of concern that their reputation will be put at risk, NGOs are therefore cautious when it comes to accepting invitations for closer cooperation. In addition, the asymmetric power position of NGOs relative to the business sector can create an uneven playing field. When NGOs and companies are invited to the negotiating table as equal partners, NGOs often suffer from capacity problems. In some cases, they are not at the table at the deciding moments.

Another issue of concern for NGOs is that the broader innovation framework is left out of the discussion. Substitution suggests, as does green chemistry, that the problem of pollution can be solved without really discussing the 'limits to growth' – the model of economic growth, competitiveness, commercialisation, and jobs itself is not up for discussion.⁵⁴ But it is actually this growth paradigm that is the real issue for some NGOs. After all, reducing production and consumption is the simplest way to combat the harmful effects of chemical substances (also see the discussion on Responsible Stagnation by De Saille & Medvecky (2016) regarding the implicit assumption of economic growth in Responsible Research and Innovation). However, this approach is not in line with the focus of the business sector on economic growth.

The changing role of the government can also lead to confusion, as the role of "partner" can come into conflict with the traditional role of the government as an inspection and supervisory

⁵⁴ See, for example, the Green Nanotech Action Agenda of the ACS Green Chemistry Institute and the Safer Nanomaterials and Nanomanufacturing Institute: *"Green nanotechnology has been making great forward progress, but the challenges presented above point to an agenda of actions where involvement by the scientific research community, industry and government could bring about changes that would be crucial to supporting a more rapid and effective commercialization of green nanotechnology. Such changes have the potential to re-establish competitive leadership in the field, with positive economic implications for the manufacturing and associated job creation."*

body. The experience of the EPA with Project XL, a pilot programme that gave companies greater flexibility to develop environmental measures is illustrative in that respect (see box).

Project XL

Project XL (*eXcellence and Leadership*) was a pilot programme of the EPA in the US that gave companies and government bodies the opportunity to work together with the EPA to develop cost-efficient environmental measures in exchange for greater flexibility with regard to the implementation of regulations and policy.

Mank (1998) describes how President Clinton, in the early 1990s, introduced an ambitious reform of the environmental regulations in the US. An assessment of the EPA's working method by the *National Academy of Public Administration* concluded that the responsibilities of the agency should be carried out via a more inclusive and flexible approach. Trade-offs between the emission of one harmful substance and the emission of another, or averaging the emission of a particular substance over various media, played an important role in this respect. Following up on this conclusion, dozens of initiatives were implemented that focused in particular on the development of "multimedia" approaches. Air, soil, and water pollution were then no longer regulated as separate and independent media but as a single ecosystem.

Project XL was the most ambitious and large-scale initiative in this series. Within two years, 50 pilot projects were started, all of them focused on greater flexibility in the environmental regulations. According to Freedman & Caffee (1996), the point of departure here was that regulations which provide greater flexibility, and at the same time require parties to assume more responsibility, offer better protection at a lower price. Project XL aimed to introduce an innovative system of licensing in order to lower the costs of compliance as well as improve environmental performance by allowing companies to try out innovative management measures that were customised to the production facility concerned instead of a one size fits all approach. In doing so, Project XL responded to an often-heard complaint by companies that environmental goals can be realised much more effectively via tailor-made environmental measures rather than through uniform and stifling regulations. Project XL focused primarily on collaboration with individual companies, whereby large companies could implement alternative plans for compliance as long as they succeeded in achieving the pollution targets agreed on beforehand with the EPA.

However, in spite of the enthusiasm for Project XL, there was also criticism. Al Iannuzzi (2001) concisely summarises the criticism of Project XL: unclear conditions, unclear legal status, high transaction costs, the appearance of *sweetheart deals* with companies, a weakening of the position of the civil society sector, and insufficient incentives for participation. The unclear legal status of the project resulted in a great deal of delay and much higher costs for companies than expected. In many pilot projects, it was not at all clear whether the EPA would actually be able to keep its own promises, as it was not certain whether the proposed reforms would be legally permitted. In some cases, this led to high costs for the participating companies.

In addition, this tailor-made approach made it more complicated for environmental groups to accurately evaluate the proposed measures. The replacement of uniform regulations by an individual tailor-made approach made it much more difficult to argue against the claims made by the industry. Local environmental groups were not capable of assessing the complex reform proposals, in which trade-offs were possible between different substances in different media. Steinzor (1998) claims that the lack of any significant public participation was the most controversial aspect of Project XL. In spite of the attempts made by the EPA to involve stakeholders more actively in the projects, the lack of clarity with respect to the role of stakeholders did not inspire any trust that the projects would actually take the role of stakeholders seriously.

According to Sexton et al (2017), five years after the start of Project XL, it was clear to proponents as well as critics that the original goals of the programme would not be realised: 'The prevailing opinion among informed observers is that Project XL has failed in practice to live up to its principles.' Of the 50 planned pilot projects, 21 had already been signed in 2000. 22 proposals were still being negotiated, 11 XL proposals were being processed, and 39 proposals had been rejected. The primary reasons for rejecting projects, according to the EPA, was that the projects could not demonstrate any substantial improvement in the environmental performance parameters. The last applications were accepted for processing in 2002.

Mark Landy (2010) described the idea of giving companies greater flexibility in exchange for their acceptance of more responsibility in the context of the governance of nanotechnology as a 'Grand Political Bargain' (2010):

'Environmentalists support government validation of nanotechnologies in exchange for industry willingness to take on a far greater amount of preproduction environmental testing and data-sharing.

Both sides thus obtain what they need the most. Industry obtains a government seal of approval for specific products and processes and may improve its overall public image in the process. Environmentalists gain the possibility of improved forms of environmental mitigation and escape the political trap of being branded as anti-technological Luddites.

Both sides also make sacrifices. Industry must endure public probing into matters it would greatly prefer to keep proprietary. Environmentalists give up the ability to reflexively stir up fear about the risks of an emerging technology as a tool for mobilizing political support and financial contributions."

The 'exchange' of a proactive approach to safety by the industry for a less stringent government supervision seems to offer an attractive perspective. By simplifying and reducing the costs of the regulatory role of government and enabling the industry to comply more quickly with regulations, it becomes possible to cut costs. However, the track record of Project XL shows that this approach also has risks. Besides the fact that the regulatory body is not automatically able to suspend existing regulations, it remains difficult to explain why certain companies are given preferential treatment. In addition, if the relationship between government and industry becomes too close, it can negatively impact public trust in the supervisory bodies, and there is a risk that civil society will no longer be able to play a role.

'Lessons' for Safe-by-Design?

Collaboration is also an important theme within Safe-by-Design. The recent brochure from the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management calls for 'intensive collaboration between specialists in specific fields of expertise such as technology, toxicology, and process and product development.' The precise structure and scope of these collaborative frameworks still have to be worked out in more detail: who collaborates with whom in the various phases of research and innovation and for what purpose? Is the focus on the practical guidance given to producers by risk researchers, on the collaborative design of new products and processes, or on being involved in regulatory matters?

The planned structure of the collaboration will unavoidably have consequences for the role distribution between the parties involved. In that regard, it is also important to watch out for potential areas of friction between the proposed and traditional roles.

For example, within the context of Safe-by-Design, consideration is given to closer collaboration between government and the business sector (this is in line with ideas on collaboration in connection with Safe-by-Design that were developed in the NANoREG project). Such collaboration offers opportunities for identifying the potential risks of nanomaterials more quickly and earlier, but it also introduces an area of tension.

On the one hand, a *buy-in* from the industry is needed in order to launch the planned collaboration. A business case has to be made for companies to adopt such initiatives: by creating added value (improved results based on key indicators such as operational efficiency, brand value, or customer retention), cost savings (in a negative sense by reducing the costs of expensive management measures and penalties, or in a positive sense for example by using less raw materials, simpler water treatment activities, or recovering energy), or by obtaining more influence on policy and regulations.

On the other hand, previous experiences show that there are risks associated with a form of collaboration between government and business sector that is too close: it can have a negative impact on public trust in the supervisory bodies, and it has consequences for the position of civil society.

5. Social responsibility

The third overarching theme is social responsibility. Based on the conviction that the chemical industry plays a leading role in opting for a safer use, management, production, and design of chemical substances, various initiatives on safer chemicals attempt to create a greater level of safety awareness within the business sector via self-regulation or pressure from external sources.

This fits in with the changing roles of stakeholders discussed in the previous chapter. Whereas in the 1960s Milton Friedman (1962) could count on broad support for his argument that making profit is the only social responsibility incumbent upon companies, few companies would today openly claim that the social impact of the company has no effect on the bottom line. This is certainly the case for the business sectors with a longer history of public resistance such as the chemical and textile industries. The ability of companies to retain their 'licence to operate' plays an important role in this regard.

Social responsibility is an important motivator for initiatives in the area of safer chemicals. Public opinion is mobilised to encourage companies to deal with chemical substances more carefully. Safer Made, an investment fund that argues for safer products and technologies in the textile and clothing industry, writes:

“Chemicals deliver certain functions to final garments. For example, fluorocarbon chemicals make rain jackets water repellent. Other chemicals are used to deliver functions to the manufacturing process; for example, sizing agents reduce the abrasiveness of yarns during fabric construction. Hazardous chemicals often end up discharged into the environment, and high-profile examples of river and surface water pollution have been a liability for the sector. **Brands are realizing that in the eyes of consumers they have a responsibility for both the chemicals on their garments and the process chemicals that are used in their manufacturing**” (p. 5)⁵⁵

The UN Global Compact simply states: *‘society expects businesses to be good actors in the community.’*⁵⁶ It should be noted that social responsibility is presented not only as an obligation but also as an opportunity. In the *Chemical Alternatives Assessment Protocol* from 2012, BizNGO points to the benefits offered by socially responsible business operations: *“businesses are under increasing pressure from governments and consumers to reduce the environmental and human health impacts of their products. [...] They recognize that reducing their reliance on chemicals of concern to human health and the environment meets market demands, keeps them ahead of regulations, reduces costs, and creates innovative and inherently safer products.”*

The business sector has launched various initiatives in response to the call for dealing with chemical substances more carefully.⁵⁷ *Together for Sustainability* is a collective initiative by chemical companies in 2011 aimed at making the value chains of the chemical industry more sustainable.⁵⁸ Another example is Fashion for Good, an initiative of the C&A Foundation in which various companies (Adidas, C&A, Galeries Lafayette Group, Kering, Target and Zalando)

⁵⁵ SaferMade (2018). Safer Chemistry Innovation in the Textile and Apparel Industry: <https://www.safermade.net/textile-report>

⁵⁶ UN Global Compact, Principle 8: Environment: <https://www.unglobalcompact.org/what-is-gc/mission/principles/principle-8>

⁵⁷ Also see Vision 2050 of the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD).

⁵⁸ <https://tfs-initiative.com/>

and sustainability consultants (Cradle to Cradle Products Innovation Institute, the Ellen MacArthur Foundation, IDH—the Sustainable Trade Initiative, Impact Hub Amsterdam, McDonough Innovation, Plug and Play, and the Sustainable Apparel Coalition) cooperate with the goal of making fashion ‘good’ again. The Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals (ZDHC) programme unites 27 major clothing brands, 81 chain partners, and 17 associates in an effort to completely eliminate the emission of hazardous substances in the textile, leather, and footwear value chains.⁵⁹

The tone of these initiatives seems to indicate that dealing with chemical substances with the necessary care requires more than simply complying with existing regulations. Safety also requires a proactive attitude towards doing more than the minimum requirements, towards taking one’s own social responsibility seriously, and towards looking for collaboration with stakeholders. This fits in with the considerations mentioned in the previous chapter, with the business sector actively positioning itself as a social partner.

These initiatives are part of a broader development in which companies take their social responsibility seriously. In 2010, Unilever launched the Sustainable Living Plan, which aimed to reduce the ecological footprint by half by 2020 (although the future course of the company is uncertain after Paul Polman stepped down).⁶⁰ The Shell oil company recently announced that it aims to reduce its carbon footprint by half by 2050.⁶¹ And 2017 saw the launch of Climate Action 100+, an investors’ initiative that aims to convince major global companies to accelerate the energy transition and to realise the goals of the Paris climate agreement.⁶²

One thing is clear: companies can play a decisive role in the safer use, production, management, and design of chemical substances. Due to their market power, the big companies in particular can force the adoption of changes throughout the value chain. Apple, for example, has substituted a series of toxic substances in their manufacturing and recycling processes for alternatives, including beryllium, mercury, lead, arsenic, PVC, phthalates, and bromine-containing flame retardants.⁶³ Hewlett-Packard (HP) has gone through a similar process by using the GreenScreen tool.⁶⁴

Social responsibility: challenges

However, it often turns out that, in practical terms, the above is ‘easier said than done’. In spite of the many initiatives in the area of social responsibility, the transition to dealing more safely with chemical substances turns out to be a difficult goal to realise. The big companies in sensitive sectors are actually the ones who become the subject of conflicting messages and a dual role as both proponents and opponents of change. While Shell presents climate goals that are more ambitious than those of many competing petrochemical companies, the company is being criticised by Milieudefensie (a Dutch environmental organisation) for causing damage to the climate.⁶⁵ In the same year that Tata Steel says that it wants its Hoogovens facility in

⁵⁹ <https://www.roadmapzero.com/about/>

⁶⁰ See: <https://www.unilever.com/sustainable-living/>

⁶¹ See: *Staring down the barrel: royal Dutch Shell tries to reckon with climate change* in The Economist of 8 Dec. 2018: <https://www.economist.com/business/2018/12/08/royal-dutch-shell-tries-to-reckon-with-climate-change>.

⁶² <http://www.climateaction100.org/>

⁶³ <https://www.apple.com/nl/environment/safer-materials/>

⁶⁴ See the BizNGO Guide to Safer Chemicals.

⁶⁵ <https://milieudefensie.nl/klimaatzaakshell>

IJmuiden to be CO₂ neutral by 2030,⁶⁶ the Province of North Holland launches a criminal investigation into the graphite emissions of the company.⁶⁷

One factor playing a role here is that companies are not monolithic organisations. Developments in one department are not immediately followed by other parts of the organisation. In addition, initiatives in the area of social responsibility can come into conflict with the responsibilities of the management towards its shareholders. Another often mentioned objection is the development of an uneven playing field: if companies voluntarily comply with stricter regulations, they may fall behind the competition.

This raises the question of to what extent self-regulation by the industry can help in implementing the transition to dealing more safely with chemical substances. The Responsible Care programme, one of the largest and oldest initiatives by the chemical industry in the area of social responsibility, provides an overview of the opportunities and challenges of self-regulation by the industry. The size of the programme alone is enough to justify the focus on Responsible Care as a prime example of an initiative in which the chemical industry shoulders its responsibility to improve the performance of the chemical sector in the area of safety, health, and the environment (see box).

The possibilities and impossibilities of self-regulation: Responsible Care

Responsible Care was developed in the early 1980s by the Chemistry Industry Association of Canada (CIAC). The programme was established in response to the diminishing public trust in the chemical industry. That trust had hit rock bottom as a result of the 1984 toxic waste disaster in Bhopal, in which thousands of people died after large quantities of methyl isocyanate were released from a pesticides plant of Union Carbide.⁶⁸ As Jean M. Bélanger, former chair of the Canadian Chemical Producers' Association (CCPA) and founder of the Responsible Care programme writes: *"In accordance with the findings of public opinion polls, industry leaders recognized that the public's concern is one of trust (Schmitt, 2002; Moffet et. al, 2004). The industry leaders chose a path that is anchored in gaining the trust of the affected communities and society in general. Trust has become the key driver of Responsible Care, which cannot be imposed, but rather requires the application of three fundamental principles, forming the cornerstones of Responsible Care: 1. Doing the right thing; 2. Being open and responsive to public concerns; 3. Caring about products from cradle to grave to cradle again."* (Bélanger et al 2009, p.3)

The programme was welcomed with a great deal of enthusiasm by chemical associations all over the world.⁶⁹ Responsible Care is now already being carried out by 58 chemical associations in over 60 countries, and 96 of the 100 biggest chemical producers in the world participate in the programme. Responsible Care is coordinated by the International Council of Chemical Associations (ICCA).⁷⁰ ICCA names Responsible Care as the main thrust of the contribution made by the chemical industry to the United Nations' SAICM programme.

Responsible Care is explicitly positioned as an ethic, a framework of moral ground principles, with management encouraging all participants of the organisation to act accordingly. The Canadian CIAC

⁶⁶ <https://www.tatasteel.nl/nl/duurzaamheid/milieu/overlast/Hinder-in-de-omgeving>

⁶⁷ <http://www.tellerreport.com/life/-criminal-investigation-into-graphite-emissions-at-tata-steel-in-ijmuiden-.Syop0Lm4.html>

⁶⁸ <http://www.bhopal.com/>

⁶⁹ As noted in an earlier exploration of green chemistry, the presence of influential and respected champions – Jean Bélanger in Canada and Robert D. Kennedy in the United States - seems to have been an important factor in empowering the movement.

⁷⁰ <https://www.icca-chem.org/about-us/>

describes *The Responsible Care*[®] ethic and principles for sustainability as follows: “We dedicate ourselves, our technology and our business practices to sustainability – the betterment of society, the environment and the economy. The principles of Responsible Care[®] are key to our business success, and compel us to: work for the improvement of people’s lives and the environment, while striving to do no harm; be accountable and responsive to the public, especially our local communities, who have the right to understand the risks and benefits of what we do; take preventative action to protect health and the environment; innovate for safer products and processes that conserve resources and provide enhanced value; engage with our partners to ensure the stewardship and security of our products, services and raw materials throughout their life cycles; understand and meet expectations for social responsibility; work with all stakeholders for public policy and standards that enhance sustainability, act to advance legal requirements and meet or exceed their letter and spirit; and promote awareness of Responsible Care, and inspire others to commit to these principles.”⁷¹

Over the years, much has been written about the impact of Responsible Care. On the one hand, the reports by the ICCA and the chemical associations show measurable progress in the performance of the chemical industry in the areas of safety, health, and sustainability (Topalovic, 2007). The level of attention focused on the Responsible Care programme, the growing number of participants all over the world, and the positioning of Responsible Care indicate that the industry itself supports the programme as an instrument for gaining the trust of the public in the chemical industry.

However, there is also criticism of the programme. Critics believe that the idealistic rhetoric is simply a cover for an attempt to escape sanctions. A critical ENDS report (2005) claims: ‘*The program does not specifically address the adoption of sustainable principles such as the utilization of safer chemicals and biomimicry to avoid injuries and decrease environmental impacts.*’ Topalovic (2007) summarises the main challenges faced by Responsible Care at the beginning of the 21st century as follows: The reports provided by the chemical companies on themselves are not always accurate and do not undergo adequate evaluation by independent parties; compliance with Responsible Care is not adequately enforced. There are no sanctions for violating the rules and codes of behaviour. This can lead to abuse of the programme for PR purposes and greenwashing. Companies are not sufficiently aware of the added value of Responsible Care and the principles of sustainable development and industrial ecology. Communication problems within companies, between companies, and with the public limit the supply of information and therefore the overall transparency. Responsible Care creates an uneven playing field, as chemical companies that are not a member of a chemical association do not have to meet the same standards. The actions of individual companies and chemical associations are not always in line with the principles of Responsible Care. Not enough attention is paid to the potential use of regulations in order to overcome the limitations of voluntary environmental programmes. (p. 2)

Attempts at self-regulation, such as Responsible Care, therefore face systemic challenges such as the free rider problem: if some companies within the sector voluntarily adopt stricter rules and other less scrupulous actors intentionally ignore the same rules, the latter can reap economic benefits. This problem is practically impossible to avoid, and it undermines confidence in the system. The report *Irresponsible Care* by the United States Public Interest Research Group (U.S. PIRG) from 2004 describes how a number of companies in the US have used the program as an excuse for postponing necessary safety measures.⁷²

Additional measures are needed to deal with the systemic challenges described above. In a research article from 2000, Andrew King and Michael Lenox emphasise the limitations of self-regulation in the

⁷¹ <https://canadianchemistry.ca/responsible-care/about-responsible-care/the-ethic-principles-of-sustainability-for-responsible-care/>

⁷² According to Prakash (200), Robert D. Kennedy, CEO of Union Carbide from 1986 to 1995, played an important role in launching Responsible Care in the United States. After the existence of the programme in Canada was brought to his attention, he became a strong advocate of rolling out the Responsible Care programme in the United States via the Chemical Manufacturers Association. However, at the same time, Union Carbide has always refused to accept responsibility for the toxic waste disaster in Bhopal. Additional study is needed to better understand the potential for tension between two different layers of responsibility.

absence of supporting legislation: *‘Responsible Care has operated up to now without explicit sanctions for malfeasance. As a result, our data suggest, it has fallen victim to enough opportunism that it includes a disproportionate number of poor performers, and its members do not improve faster than non-members. Thus, whatever the strength of the institutional forces that Responsible Care brings to bear on its members -and these forces appear considerable- they have not been enough to counteract opportunism. Since Responsible Care represents a leading example of self-regulation in the world, our findings highlight the difficulty of creating self-regulation without explicit sanctions.’* (p. 713)

The national chemical associations have responded to this criticism in a variety of different ways. According to Topalovic (2007, p. 10-11), the American Chemistry Council (ACC) has made a ‘hybrid Responsible Care/ISO 14001 environmental management system’ mandatory. In Canada, the Canadian Chemical Producers’ Association (CCPA) has appointed independent evaluation teams from the industry. In addition, all members of the CCPA are required to submit annual reports on the emissions and quantities of waste produced by the company each year. In contrast, the national chemical associations in Europe have been less active in the implementation of external monitoring. Only the Chemical Industries Association in the United Kingdom has set hard emission targets since 2003.

To summarise, we can say that Responsible Care has been the largest initiative by the chemical industry aimed at making companies more accountable in a structured manner. It is a long-term programme that is anchored in chemical associations all over the world. In spite of this success, there is also criticism, in particular due to the voluntary character of the programme and the problem of free riders. In some countries, this criticism has been dealt with via stricter measures such as ISO certification.

‘Lessons’ for Safe-by-Design?

The responsibility of producers themselves plays an important role in the discussion concerning Safe-by-Design. Safe-by-Design is the expression of a guiding normative ideal that all the parties concerned must work out together. In the Letter to Parliament of 5 June 2018 on the desired transition from remediation and management to the prevention of environmental risks and hazards, the State Secretary of Infrastructure and Water Management writes *‘In the next two years, we will search for leading companies, companies that attach a great deal of importance to technology and innovation and work to promote Socially Responsible Innovation. Together with these companies, I aim to launch collaborative activities (pilots/demonstration projects) with the goal of making Safe-by-Design operational.’*

The exploration of initiatives in the area of safer chemicals demonstrates that a guiding normative ideal can help in motivating target groups. Within the framework of the ‘licence to operate’, the chemical and textile industries are developing a range of initiatives for the responsible management of chemical substances, at their own initiative or in response to NGOs. Initiatives such as Together for Sustainability, Fashion for Good, the Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals programme, and Responsible Care bring producers, retailers, and NGOs together in the search for a cleaner and safer world.

A previous study into green chemistry indicated that the definition of a positive philosophy of chemistry (‘green chemistry prevents the release of undesirable hazardous substances via the design of chemical products and processes’) made it possible for a variety of different interest groups to support the goals of the movement. Analogously, by working out the further details of a guiding perspective, it might be possible, within the framework of the further implementation of Safe-by-Design, to ensure that various stakeholders also align themselves with the movement.

However, the experience acquired through Responsible Care shows that the possibilities of self-regulation are limited. Simply appealing to the moral conscience of the parties involved might therefore not be sufficient to realise the transition to a safer use of chemical substances. Topalovic (2007) writes:

According to Willard (2005), there exists a proper mix between legislation and voluntary initiatives. Too much legislation can be too costly, as was the case in the command and control era of the past. However, too little legislation may not provide the necessary incentives to ensure compliance from industry." (p. 32)

Voluntary initiatives should therefore be accompanied by mechanisms to enforce compliance: self-regulation thrives best in the shadow of hierarchy.⁷³

⁷³ In an interview, Kees Le Blansch pointed to this memorable statement by the German political scientist Fritz W. Scharpf.

6. Conclusion

This brief exploration of the world of safer chemicals shows a mixed picture. On the one hand, the transition to the safer use, production, management, and design of chemical substances appears to be a complex challenge. A great deal of energy is being invested in the development of databases and tools to facilitate the safer management, selection, and development of chemical substances. However, as it turns out, keeping these databases up-to-date, guaranteeing the quality of the data, identifying the relationships, making these resources available to the intended target groups, and providing effective guidance to users in their search for safer alternatives turns out to be an enormous challenge. All kinds of attempts are being made to initiate new forms of collaboration, but there is also a lack of mutual understanding between the various disciplines involved. This is due to the lack of a common language, a lack of trust in relation to the hidden agendas of the various stakeholders, and protection of the interests of each party's own constituents. Various initiatives are also being developed to engage producers on the basis of social responsibility, but well-intended initiatives face the limitations of self-regulation.

On the other hand, things are happening on many fronts; a lot of examples of successful substitution can be found. For example, the BizNGO Guide to Safer Chemicals refers to how Hewlett-Packard, with the help of the GreenScreen tool, replaced a series of substances of very high concern such as phthalates, brominated flame retardants, PVC, bisphenol A, beryllium, and perfluorinated compounds (p. 37).⁷⁴ The *Business Guide to Safer Chemicals* published by Chemical Watch in 2018 describes how clothing producer Páramo replaced substances of concern such as perfluorinated compounds (PFCs) and polytetrafluoroethylenes (ePTFEs) by less harmful alternatives.⁷⁵

This exploration of the world of safer chemicals offers some suggestions for the further implementation of Safe-by-Design.

- The central concept underlying Safe-by-Design, namely taking safety considerations into account from the first stage of development, sounds simple. However, the exploration of the safer chemicals theme makes it clear how complicated it is to realise this self-evident concept in practice. To make a well-considered choice for an alternative that has proven to be safer, it is necessary to first connect a very diverse set of data on an ever-growing collection of chemical substances. The challenge for Safe-by-Design is even greater, as this concept includes nanotechnology and biotechnology in addition to chemical substances.
- The practical application of safety considerations is not simply a question of *developing* information, but also of effectively *transferring* this information to the user. This requires risk researchers to take on a guiding and advisory role. The suggestion for Safe-by-Design is not to develop knowledge via a top-down approach, from the traditional risk research perspective, but to do so in collaboration with the intended user and within the context of the application: in what *form* does the knowledge already available have to be presented to the diverse target groups so that the knowledge provided actually meets the knowledge

⁷⁴ BizNGO Guide to Safer Chemicals (Version 1.0):

https://www.bizngo.org/static/ee_images/uploads/resources/guide_safer-chemicals_full.pdf

⁷⁵ Chemical Watch Business Guide to Safer Chemicals: <https://chemicalwatch.com/report-bgsc4e/>

requirements of the user? What kind of *guidance* do developers, producers, and consumers need to actually take considerations of safety into account in the design phase?

- The exploration of safer chemicals suggests that new forms of collaboration offer opportunities, but can also lead to tensions between new and traditional roles of stakeholders. Which forms of collaboration are advocated by Safe-by-Design? Who works with whom in which phases of research and innovation, and in which role? And what are the potential consequences of this collaboration for the roles of stakeholders?
- A guiding normative ideal can help in motivating target groups, but an appeal to morality is not in itself sufficient to lead to a change in direction with regard to the safer use of chemical substances. In addition to self-regulation, compliance monitoring remains necessary. In other words, prevention cannot completely replace management.⁷⁶

These considerations indicate why it is so difficult to reach agreement on apparently simple questions such as, ‘What is Safe-by-Design?’ The further implementation of Safe-by-Design is not only a question of formulating a new design approach focused on safety. By definition, it also requires policy choices regarding the role of government in relation to the business sector and civil society, as well as the desired balance between precautionary measures and innovation.

⁷⁶ Also see Burnett, M.L. (1998): The Pollution Prevention Act of 1990: A Policy Whose Time Has Come or Symbolic Legislation? *Environmental Management* 22(2):213-224.

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BizNGO

<https://www.bizngo.org>

BizNGO is a collaborative framework of companies, environmental organisations, government entities, and universities that is focused on the use of safer chemicals in the economy. BizNGO works with companies from various sectors such as the electronics, healthcare, retail, construction, and cleaning agent sectors. Participating NGOs include Health Care Without Harm, Electronics Take Back Coalition, Healthy Building Network and the Investor Environmental Health Network. According to BizNGO, the dialogue between companies and NGOs helps in understanding the concerns regarding the health effects of chemical products on people and the environment and in identifying such problems at an earlier stage. This makes it possible for producers to respond more quickly to these developments.

BizNGO was established in 2006. It is a network organisation: in principle, everyone who endorses the *BizNGO Principles for Safer Chemicals* can participate. The BizNGO principles consist of 4 guidelines for the substance policy of participating companies and their suppliers:

1. *Know and disclose product chemistry.*
2. *Assess and avoid hazards.*
3. *Commit to continuous improvement.*
4. *Support public policies and industry standards that advance the above three principles.*

BizNGO has various workgroups, including the Safer Chemicals Work Group, the Alternatives Assessments Work Group and the Policy Work Group. BizNGO holds an annual meeting. The next meeting is scheduled to take place from 10 to 11 December 2019 in Boston.

BizNGO is an initiative of Clean Production Action. The mission of Clean Production Action is to design and deliver solutions for green chemicals, sustainable materials, and environmentally friendly products. Clean Production Action was founded in 2001. It is the driving force behind BizNGO network,⁷⁷ the GreenScreen^{®78} and the Chemical Footprint Project.⁷⁹ Clean Production Action works closely together with existing networks all over the world to learn about new technological trends and associated environmental issues, and to create and communicate real solutions. Clean Production Action is a project of the Tides Center.

Important persons within Clean Production Action are Mark Rossi, Cheri Peele, Beverley Thorpe, Alexandra McPherson and Ken Geiser. Dr Mark Rossi is presently director of Clean Production Action. He develops new instruments and programmes that aim to encourage the use of safer chemicals and sustainable materials. He is also one of the founders of GreenScreen. Cheri Peele drafted the BizNGO Chemical Alternatives Assessment Protocol. She collaborates with the government and business sector in the area of safer chemicals, and is a consultant to Clean Production Action. Beverley Thorpe is co-director of Clean Production Action. She has been involved in researching and implementing clean production methods since 1986. She was co-founder of the *United Nations Environment Programme for Cleaner Production*. Ken Geiser is

⁷⁷ <https://www.bizngo.org/>

⁷⁸ <https://www.greenscreenchemicals.org/>

⁷⁹ <https://www.chemicalfootprint.org/>

chair of the Board of Directors of Clean Production Action. Clean Production Action is based in Massachusetts, USA.

BizNGO Chemical Alternatives Assessment Protocol⁸⁰

The BizNGO *Chemical Alternatives Assessment Protocol* is an instrument for companies to identify safer alternatives for substances of concern that are technically and economically feasible. The protocol builds further on the work of the Lowell Centre for Sustainable Production, the Design for the Environment programme of the EPA, the Toxics Reduction Institute (TURI), the Interstate Chemicals Clearinghouse (IC2) and ChemSec. The protocol consists of seven steps:

- Step 1: Substances of concern are the starting point of the search for alternatives.
- Steps 2 and 3: A company has to know why the substance has been added to the material or product in order to be able to determine the possible alternatives.
- Step 4: A chemical hazard assessment is crucial for determining an alternative.
- Step 5: After the hazard assessment, the technical and economic performance criteria of alternatives can be compared.
- Step 6: *Life-cycle assessment* is necessary if the alternatives lead to significant changes in the production process.
- Step 7: The company has then identified one or more alternatives that are safer for people and the environment, and that are technically and economically feasible.

⁸⁰ <https://www.bizngo.org/alternatives-assessment/chemical-alternatives-assessment-protocol>

Figure 1 - Flow diagram of the BizNGO Chemical Alternatives Assessment Protocol. The diagram builds further on Lavoie et al (2010): Chemical Alternatives Assessment, *Environmental Science and Technology* 44(24): 9244-9, and Rossi et al (2006): Alternatives Assessment Framework, Lowell Center for Sustainable Production.

ChemHAT

www.chemhat.org

ChemHAT, the Chemical Hazard and Alternatives Toolbox, is an online database with user-friendly information that can provide protection against the potentially harmful effects of chemical substances.

ChemHAT is based on the simple concept that we can protect ourselves if we know what the hazards are of a chemical substance. Sometimes it is sufficient to wear gloves or to ventilate the space in question. But ChemHAT does more than just look at measures that can be taken retroactively to reduce exposure to a safe level. The idea behind ChemHAT is to provide an answer to the question, 'Can this task be completed without the use of hazardous chemical substances?' Based on previous experiences, it often turns out to be possible to avoid the use of hazardous substances or to find a replacement substance.

ChemSec Marketplace

<https://marketplace.chemsec.org/>

Marketplace is a free business to business website where buyers and sellers of chemical alternatives can find each other. Providers of safer alternatives can offer their safer products here, and downstream users can search for effective substitutes for the hazardous substances in their products.

In recent years, companies in a variety of sectors, including the electronics, building, and textile sectors, have made significant progress in replacing hazardous substances by safer alternatives. However, finding these alternatives is often difficult. Marketplace connects providers and purchasers in the same way that eBay, Airbnb or Marktplaats do: users themselves indicate whether they are looking for an alternative or offering one.

Marketplace is an initiative of ChemSec (The International Chemical Secretariat), an independent non-profit organisation that advocates a world free of hazardous chemical substances.⁸¹ ChemSec is an advocate of progressive substance-related legislation, and also exerts pressure on companies to make the transition to non-toxic alternatives. It does so via international research, international collaboration, and the development of practical tools.

ChemSec was established in 2002 by four Swedish environmental organisations: the Swedish Nature Protection Association, WWF Sweden, Friends of the Earth Sweden, and Nature & Youth Sweden.⁸² These organisations still form the core management of ChemSec. The secretariat is based in Goteborg. In 2017, the organisation had total revenues of 7,285,556 Swedish Crowns (688,562 euros).⁸³

⁸¹ <https://chemsec.org/>

⁸² <https://chemsec.org/about-us/board/>

⁸³ See the 2017 annual report: https://chemsec.org/app/uploads/2018/05/2017-Financial-Statement_180409.pdf

ChemSec is represented in the executive committee of IPEN, the GreenScreen® steering committee, the OECD ad hoc group on substitution and alternatives assessment, and the ISC3 Advisory Council. ChemSec is also a member of EEB, the *European Environmental Bureau*.

Design for the Environment

<https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice/design-environment-programs-initiatives-and-projects>

In the 1990s, the United States Environmental Protection Agency developed the Design for the Environment (DfE) programme. The programme started as a voluntary initiative aimed at helping companies to take into account health and environmental effects in the design and production of commercial products and processes. DfE investigated the potential health and environmental risks in industrial sectors. The programme encouraged collaboration between researchers, NGOs, and the business sector in order to find innovative and cost-effective solutions. This collaboration resulted in a broad range of supporting instruments such as Comparative Technology Substitutes Assessments (CTSAs), Best Practices Guidance and Life-Cycle Assessments.

At the end of the 1990s, the programme focused more on safer chemicals. In response to increasing public interest in the safety of substances in household and other consumer products, DfE worked primarily on the evaluation of substances that were considered an urgent problem, and on the recognition of companies that adopted a policy of choosing safer ingredients for their products. This led to the labelling of safer products at the beginning of the 21st century. DfE developed a certification programme on the basis of criteria for safer substances, which made it possible for companies to differentiate their products in the market. It also enabled purchasers to consciously make a choice for safer products. In 2015, this label was renamed the Safer Choice label (more information on Safer Choice is provided further on in this appendix).

The DfE programme also developed a variety of programmes and instruments that made it easier for stakeholders to determine the health and environmental effects of chemical substances, including:

- ***DfE Alternatives Assessments***, making it possible for environmental organisations, producers, researchers, and other interested parties to collaborate on determining the health and environmental effects of potentially safer chemical alternatives. The business sector can use the results of this collaboration to determine safer alternatives.
- ***DfE Life-Cycle Assessments (LCA)***. LCA studies determine the potential environmental effects of a product, material, process, or activity. The results of these studies can help companies to reduce the environmental impact of products and processes.
- ***DfE Pesticide Pilot Projects***. This project applies the DfE Safer Product labelling programme to approved antimicrobial pesticides and bio-pesticides.
- ***Safer Detergents Stewardship Initiative (SDSI)***. This initiative recognises companies that have a policy of using only safer surfactant substances.
- ***DfE Workplace Best Practices*** offers practical information on reducing pollution and protecting workers and consumers. These best practices are developed by DfE in

collaboration with the chemical industry, the SME sector, suppliers, local governments, and environmental organisations.

DIAMONDS - Data Infrastructure for Applying Models ON Design and Safety

https://www.tno.nl/media/2102/diamonds_leaflet.pdf

(From the brochure:)

Innovations in a great many fields of application, such as chemistry, cosmetics, foodstuffs, and medicines, depend on the development of new chemical molecules with improved properties, such as coatings with better colour characteristics, food packaging that provide better protection, et cetera. Each of these fields of application has its own regulatory framework, in which the toxicological profiles of these new chemical compounds are characterised.

Until recently, the potential harmful effects of new chemical substances could only be determined for individual substances via animal trials. Nowadays, toxicological profiles can also be determined by integrating data from various disciplines. With the introduction of the Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOP) concept, in which relationships are determined between chemical structures and the results of toxicological studies, it becomes possible to optimise the developmental phase of new chemical substances and to better predict the toxicological profiles that are needed for registration purposes.

TNO is developing an infrastructure with statistical instruments and text-mining methods that is intended to facilitate characterising the toxicological properties of new chemical molecules with the help of data and analyses from a variety of disciplines (computational chemistry, toxicokinetics, system biology, bioinformatics, statistics, and toxicological risk analysis), in combination with alternative experimental models for biological verification. This approach is referred to as 'DIAMONDS: Data Infrastructure for Applying Models ON Design and Safety. The goal is to determine the toxicological profile of a chemical molecule as early and cost effectively as possible.

TNO - Risk Analysis for Products In Development (RAPID)

RAPID researches the quality and safety of chemical substances, food ingredients/products, medicines, and nanoparticles. Traditionally, the research carried out in RAPID focuses on national/international legal frameworks, but the focus is increasingly shifting to earlier process stages, such as the development of new ingredients and products, for example nanomaterials, new protein sources in foods, and medicines.

The human health risks associated with substances increasingly rely on modelling approaches in order to reduce costs and obtain results more rapidly. RAPID does this by combining a thorough knowledge of risk analysis and statistics with practical experience in innovative experimental research (toxicology, chemical analysis, sensor technology, human exposure et cetera). Integrated strategies are being developed that are as effective as possible in predicting the human health risks and that minimise the use of animal testing. RAPID has recourse to

special facilities in the area of chemical analysis, including Accelerated Mass Spectrometry, dustiness analysis of nanomaterials, and sensor technology (optical-chemical, spectroscopic and biochemical sensors).

Global Chemicals Outlook

<https://www.unenvironment.org/explore-topics/chemicals-waste/what-we-do/policy-and-governance/global-chemicals-outlook>

The **Global Chemicals Outlook: Towards Sound Management of Chemicals** was published in 2013. The report collected scientific, technical, and socio-economic information on the sound management of chemical substances. It presented trends and indicators for the production, transport, use, and removal of chemical products, as well as the health and environmental effects and economic consequences of these trends, the costs of failing to act and the benefits of acting, and the instruments and approaches needed for sound management.

The **Global Chemicals Outlook II – From Legacies to Innovative Solutions: Implementing the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development** was published in April 2019. This report attempts to make policymakers and other stakeholders aware of the importance of the sound management of chemical substances for sustainable development. It looks at global trends with regard to the global goal of minimising the harmful consequences of chemical substances and chemical waste in 2020. The report concludes that this goal will not be realised before 2020. Solutions do exist, but they require a more ambitious commitment by all stakeholders.

The report was prepared within a period of three years with the cooperation of more than 400 experts and scientists all over the world.

GoodGuide

<https://www.goodguide.com>

GoodGuide provides consumers with product information that helps in making better informed purchasing decisions. Well-informed consumers make better decisions and, by doing so, help to implement the transition to safer, healthier, and more sustainable products. The team behind GoodGuide consists of more than 50 chemists, toxicologists, and experts in the fields of life-cycle assessment and regulations applicable to chemical substances.

GoodGuide scores products on the basis of information on the ingredients and authoritative sources on chemical regulations, thereby giving consumers direct access to understandable information about the product. GoodGuide collects data on products based on publicly available information (via labels and websites) or information from the producer. Every product page lists the information source.

The GoodGuide website and mobile app are used daily by consumers to decipher product labels, to identify ingredients, and to make informed choices.

GreenScreen®

GreenScreen® is an instrument used to assess chemical risks and thereby to identify substances of concern and generate safer alternatives.⁸⁴ GreenScreen® was established in 2007 and is used by companies, governments, and NGOs to facilitate product design and development, to purchase raw materials and other materials, and to carry out alternatives assessments (legally required or voluntary). GreenScreen® builds further on the 12 principles of green chemistry and the alternatives assessment method of the Design for the Environment programme of the EPA, in which the available data on the inherent properties of a substance, such as toxicity and health and environmental effects, are presented in a risk table. This risk assessment results in a benchmark that allows for a straightforward comparison between different substances (see figure below). GreenScreen® therefore allows companies to sort substances in terms of preference. GreenScreen® is used by companies such as Walmart, Hewlett Packard (HP), Levi Strauss & Co, and Apple.

GreenScreen® is an initiative of Clean Production Action. The mission of Clean Production Action is to design and deliver solutions for green chemicals, sustainable materials, and environmentally friendly products. Clean Production Action works closely together with existing networks all over the world to learn about new technological trends and associated environmental issues, and to create and communicate real solutions. Clean Production Action is also the initiator of the BizNGO network,⁸⁵ and the Chemical Footprint Project⁸⁶ (see further on in this appendix). Clean Production Action was established in 2001 and is based in Massachusetts, USA.

⁸⁴ <https://www.greenscreenchemicals.org/learn/what-is-greenscreen>

⁸⁵ <https://www.bizngo.org/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.chemicalfootprint.org/>

Figure 2 - Green Screen Benchmarks. See www.greenscreenchemicals.org

IC2 Chemical Hazard Assessment Database

<http://www.theic2.org/hazard-assessment>

The Interstate Chemicals Clearinghouse (IC2) is a collaborative network of local and national governments that strive to promote a clean living environment, a healthy society, and a thriving economy via the development and utilisation of safer chemical substances and products. IC2 is a programme of the Northeast Waste Management Officials' Association (NEWMOA).

IC2 developed the Chemical Hazard Assessment Database, which provides insight into assessments based on GreenScreen® and the Quick Chemical Assessment Tool (QCAT). The goal is to raise awareness of assessments of substances of concern and to promote transparency.

ISO14001

<https://www.nen.nl/NEN-Shop/ISO-14001-en-ISO-14004-1.htm>

ISO 14001 is a standard that describes the requirements that an environmental management system must meet. This standard describes an environmental management system according to a model based on the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle (PDCA).

The ISO 14001 environmental management system aims to identify, prioritise, and then to manage and improve environmental aspects in a systematic fashion, in order to ensure that the environmental goals of the organisation can be achieved.

Environmental aspects are the interactions between the activities, products, and services of an organisation that can lead to environmental effects. Examples include emissions to soil, water, and air as well as sound, radiation, and energy consumption. An organisation must take into account the environmental aspects that it can manage, for example emissions resulting from its own production process as well as those that it can influence, such as the energy consumption of its products in the use phase.

ISO 14001 does not specify what an acceptable environmental burden is. The organisation has to determine this itself, based on an analysis of its environmental aspects and their potential effects on the environment, taking into account the legal requirements and in communication with stakeholders. ISO 14001 sets as a condition that an organisation must continually strive to improve its environmental performance, in other words to reduce its environmental burden.

NAS Framework to Chemical Alternatives

<https://www.nap.edu/catalog/18872/a-framework-to-guide-selection-of-chemical-alternatives>

The regulatory framework for chemical substances has traditionally been focused on the harmful health effects of commonly occurring substances, including carcinogenicity. Thanks to scientific research, our understanding of how chemical substances are harmful to human health and the environment continues to expand. The identification of substances of concern has led to a growing number of national and local governments to take measures that go beyond the existing regulation of substances at the federal level. There is also a growing interest in approaches for ensuring that the substitution of substances of concern takes place as carefully as possible. The goal is to prevent regrettable substitutions.

Alternative assessments are instruments that can help stakeholders to identify hazardous substances and develop safer alternatives. The *NAS Framework to Chemical Alternatives* offers a framework for determining which replacement substances are potentially safer, on the basis of known health and environmental risks. This framework is based on the findings of regulatory bodies, academic institutions, et cetera. In addition to risk assessments, the framework also contains suggestions for life-cycle thinking, so that the potential impact of a chemical substance in all phases of development, including production, use, and removal, is

taken into account. The framework also provides tips on how new sources of information such as computational models can be used to supplement traditional toxicological data.

The framework helps to weigh the advantages and disadvantages of replacement substances, also in comparison to other factors such as functionality, efficiency, process safety, and raw material consumption. Case studies are used to demonstrate how various users can utilise the framework in a variety of decision-making contexts. This information is intended for the chemical industry, environmental experts and activists, ecologists, and governments.

OECD eChemPortal

<https://www.echemportal.org>

The eChemPortal offers free access to information on chemical substances - including commonly used substances, new industrial substances, pesticides and biocides - via links to data sources and initiatives by and for governments at the regional, national, and international level. The eChemPortal also explains the classification of substances on the basis of national and regional classification schemes and the *Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals* (GHS). In addition, the eChemPortal provides information on the exposure to and use of chemical substances.

The eChemPortal is an initiative of the *Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development* (OECD), with contributions from governments and other stakeholders, and was developed in collaboration with the *European Chemicals Agency* (ECHA). The portal contributes to implementing the recommendation of the *Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management* (SAICM) to facilitate public access to information and knowledge on chemical substances.

The eChemPortal was launched in 2007. In the initial phase, users could search for substances based on the name or identification number of the substance. Whereas the initial focus was on information about the risks of existing substances, as the number of available data sources grew, new industrial substances, pesticides, and biocides also came into the picture, as well as risk assessments and GHS classifications. In 2010, the eChemPortal underwent a thorough revision to allow users to be able to search on the basis of chemical characteristics in addition to the name and identification number of a substance. The search results provide access to the complete datasets in the participating databanks. In 2015, a search functionality on the basis of GHS classification was added to the portal. Users can access all the information on each substance in participating databanks, and they can also follow which classifications have been re-evaluated by regulatory bodies or intergovernmental organisations.

OECD Substitution and Alternatives Assessment Toolbox

<http://www.oecdsaatoolbox.org/>

The OECD Substitution and Alternatives Assessment Toolbox is the initiative of an organisation established in 2012, the *Ad Hoc Group on Substitution of Harmful Chemicals* of the OECD. In 2013, this group published the OECD Meta-Review, containing an overview of instruments and methods, knowledge sources and gaps in the member states in the area of substitution. The Meta-Review served as the basis for the Toolbox.

The SAAT Toolbox is an attempt to collect the wide variety of information available on substitution and alternative assessments in a well-organised and understandable manner. The toolbox consists of four categories:

- *Alternatives Assessment decision aid*: a searchable list with instruments and data sources for the risk assessment of chemical substances.
- *Assessment frameworks for substitution*: an overview of assessment frameworks for evaluating chemical alternatives, including substitution manuals.
- *Case studies and other resources*: links to case studies, toolkits, and product evaluations that provide examples of various approaches to substitution.
- *Regulations and restrictions*: a list of regulations and restrictions in the member states of the OECD which are the driving force behind substitution.

PRIO

<https://www.kemi.se/en/prio-start>

PRIO is an initiative of the Swedish Chemical Agency (KemI), which aims to assist environmental managers, purchasers, and product developers in Sweden to determine the environmental and health risks of chemical substances and to decide whether risk reduction measures are needed. PRIO also provides information for environmental and health inspectors, risk researchers, and everyone else who has an influence on how chemical substances are dealt with. PRIO offers users a step-by-step plan for identifying environmental effects. It also provides information on the properties and classification of chemical substances, as well as assistance in making the right choices in relation to purchasing, product development, and risk management. The emphasis on risk reduction measures for chemical substances follows from the goal of the Swedish Parliament to contribute to a non-toxic environment. This goal is in line with the goals of REACH. PRIO helps users to comply with REACH and contribute to sustainable development. PRIO connects various environmental and health related criteria to chemical substances, and gives examples of risk reduction measures for the substances concerned.

Project XL

Project XL (*eXcellence and Leadership*) was a pilot programme of the EPA in the US that gave companies and government bodies the opportunity to work together with the EPA to develop cost-efficient environmental measures in exchange for greater flexibility with regard to the implementation of regulations and policy. Mank (1998) describes how President Clinton, in the early 1990s, introduced an ambitious reform of the environmental regulations in the US. An assessment of the EPA's working method by the *National Academy of Public Administration* concluded that the responsibilities of the agency should be carried out via a more inclusive and flexible approach. Trade-offs between the emission of one harmful substance and the emission of another, or averaging the emission of a particular substance over various media, played an important role in this respect. Following up on this conclusion, dozens of initiatives were implemented that focused in particular on the development of 'multimedia' approaches. Air, soil, and water pollution were then no longer regulated as separate and independent media but as a single eco-system (until then, regulations for the different media were contained in separate pieces of legislation such as the Clean Water Act and the Clean Air Act). Besides the risk of overlapping or conflicting measures, a major disadvantage of this strict compartmentalisation was that regulations in the area of air-pollution, for example, could lead to simply moving the emissions over to the soil or water compartment. The 1994 'Common Sense Initiative' of the EPA was one of the early examples of regulatory reform, whereby the industry was given greater freedom in reducing emissions, as long as certain environmental targets were achieved, than was the case in the traditional approach where specific management measures were mandated. An 'ecosystem-based approach' was intended to replace the prescriptive command-and-control approach. The *Environmental Leadership Programme* was another initiative that gave companies greater flexibility if they made a bigger effort to achieve specific environmental targets.

Project XL in 1995 was the most ambitious and large-scale initiative in this series. Within two years, 50 pilot projects were started, all of them focused on greater flexibility in the environmental regulations. According to Freedman & Caffee (1996), the point of departure here was that regulations which provide greater flexibility, and at the same time require parties to assume more responsibility, offer better protection at a lower price. Project XL aimed to introduce an innovative system of licensing in order to lower the costs of compliance as well as improve environmental performance by allowing companies to try out innovative management measures that were customised to the production facility concerned instead of a one size fits all approach. In doing so, Project XL responded to an often-heard complaint by companies that environmental goals can be realised much more effectively via tailor-made environmental measures rather than via uniform and stifling regulations.

Project XL consisted of four components, focused on: 1) individual companies; 2) sector-wide initiatives; 3) agencies regulated by the EPA; 4) collaboration with social partners. The primary focus was on collaboration with individual companies, with large companies being able to implement alternative plans for compliance as long as they succeeded in achieving the pollution targets agreed on beforehand with the EPA. Predefined norm values for specific substances per medium were replaced by predefined maximum values for the entire production facility. This made it possible for companies to take trade-offs between different substances or media into account in calculating emissions or to average these emissions.

However, in spite of the enthusiasm for Project XL, there was also criticism. Al Iannuzzi (2001) concisely summarises the criticism of Project XL: unclear conditions, unclear legal status, high transaction costs, the appearance of sweetheart deals with companies, a weakening of the position of the civil society sector, and insufficient incentives for participation.

The unclear legal status of the project resulted in a great deal of delay and much higher costs for companies than expected. In many pilot projects, it was not at all clear whether the EPA would actually be able to keep its own promises, as it was not certain whether the proposed reforms would be legally permissible. In some cases, this led to high costs for the participating companies.

In addition, this tailor-made approach made it much more complicated for environmental groups to accurately evaluate the proposed measures. The replacement of uniform regulations by an individual tailor-made approach would also make it much more difficult to argue against the claims made by the industry. Local environmental groups would not have the resources to evaluate the complex reform proposals, in which trade-offs were possible between different substances in different media. Steinzor (1998) claims that the lack of any significant public participation was the most controversial aspect of Project XL. In spite of the attempts made by the EPA to involve stakeholders more actively in the projects, the lack of clarity with respect to the role of stakeholders did not inspire any trust that the projects would actually take the role of stakeholders seriously.

According to Sexton et al (2017), five years after the start of Project XL, it was clear to proponents as well as critics that the original goals of the programme would not be realised: *'The prevailing opinion among informed observers is that Project XL has failed in practice to live up to its principles.'* Of the 50 planned pilot projects, 21 had already been signed in 2000. 22 proposals were still being negotiated, 11 XL proposals were being processed, and 39 proposals had been rejected. The primary reasons for rejecting projects, according to the EPA, was that the projects could not demonstrate any substantial improvement in the environmental performance parameters. The last applications were accepted for processing in 2002..

Quick Chemical Assessment Tool (QCAT)

<https://fortress.wa.gov/ecy/publications/documents/1404033.pdf>

The Department of Ecology of the State of Washington in the US developed the Quick Chemical Assessment Tool (QCAT), a simplified version of GreenScreen®. QCAT enables smaller companies to quickly find chemical alternatives. QCAT offers users a standard for objectively assessing and comparing the risks of chemical substances. However, as QCAT is much less extensive than GreenScreen®, it leads to an increased risk of 'regrettable substitution', the replacement of one harmful substance by another.

Responsible Care

Responsible Care was developed in the early 1980s by the Chemistry Industry Association of Canada (CIAC). The programme was established in response to the diminishing public trust in the chemical industry. That trust had hit rock bottom as a result of the 1984 toxic waste disaster in Bhopal, in which thousands of people died after large quantities of methyl isocyanate were released from a pesticides plant of Union Carbide.⁸⁷

Responsible Care is now already being carried out by 58 chemical associations in over 60 countries, and 96 of the 100 biggest chemical producers in the world participate in the programme. Responsible Care is coordinated by the International Council of Chemical Associations (ICCA).⁸⁸ ICCA positions Responsible Care as the main thrust of the contribution made by the chemical industry to the United Nations' Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management (SAICM) programme.

Whereas initially Responsible Care focused primarily on the management of chemical risks via process safety and dealing carefully with chemical substances, more recently, according to Bélanger (2009), the focus has shifted to preventive chemistry.

Responsible Care is explicitly positioned as an *ethic*, a framework of moral ground principles, with management encouraging all participants of the organisation to act accordingly. The Canadian CIAC describes *The Responsible Care® ethic and principles for sustainability* as follows:

We dedicate ourselves, our technology and our business practices to sustainability – the betterment of society, the environment and the economy. The principles of Responsible Care® are key to our business success, and compel us to:

- work for the improvement of people's lives and the environment, while striving to do no harm;
- be accountable and responsive to the public, especially our local communities, who have the right to understand the risks and benefits of what we do;
- take preventative action to protect health and the environment;
- innovate for safer products and processes that conserve resources and provide enhanced value;
- engage with our partners to ensure the stewardship and security of our products, services and raw materials throughout their life cycles;
- understand and meet expectations for social responsibility;
- work with all stakeholders for public policy and standards that enhance sustainability, act to advance legal requirements and meet or exceed their letter and spirit; and,
- promote awareness of Responsible Care, and inspire others to commit to these principles.⁸⁹

Whereas in the initial years Responsible Care focused primarily on the management of chemical risks via process safety and dealing carefully with chemical substances, more recently, according to Bélanger (2009), the focus has shifted to preventive chemistry.

“Responding to public concerns through an ethical approach requires sensitivity to the changing nature of concerns over time. Responsible Care has been successful in this, as

⁸⁷ <http://www.bhopal.com/>

⁸⁸ <https://www.icca-chem.org/about-us/>

⁸⁹ <https://canadianchemistry.ca/responsible-care/about-responsible-care/the-ethic-principles-of-sustainability-for-responsible-care/>

evidenced by its evolution to include verification, community advisory panels and the sustainable principles of green chemistry. The most recent revision of the ethic includes preventive and green engineering principles (CCPA, 2008a). To maintain public trust, the industry must engage in ongoing and visible responsiveness to what is currently of public and scientific concern. In the early 1980s, the issues dominating the public agenda were closely related to plant operations or movement of chemicals. Since then, concerns have broadened to focus on product stewardship, including the use of the chemicals, and are currently dominated by concerns relating to sustainability and climate change.”

Nevertheless, the Responsible Care reports in most countries seem to focus in particular on process safety. For example, the 2015 Responsible Care Rapport of the Royal Association of the Dutch Chemical Industry (VNCI) does name sustainable entrepreneurship and circular economy as new attention points:

“The chemicals sector is fully engaged in promoting sustainability. It attaches a great deal of importance to improving its performance in the areas of safety, health, and the environment as well as its communication in those areas. For example, all the members of the Royal Association of the Dutch Chemical Industry (VNCI) participate in the global Responsible Care (RC) programme. Responsible Care includes process safety, working conditions, environment, transport/transport safety, communication on Responsible Care, security, and product stewardship (chain management). In recent years, the VNCI has extended the scope of the Responsible Care programme to include sustainable entrepreneurship, and has focused it more explicitly on improvements within the value chain.”⁹⁰

However, the measurable results in the report primarily involve compliance with existing safety guidelines such as REACH and occupational health & safety legislation. In its report, in addition to sustainability, the VNCI also gives priority to reducing red tape and strengthening the competitive position of the Dutch industry.

In his evaluation of the Responsible Care programme, Aseem Prakash writes:⁹¹

The implications of private codes for business strategy and public policy have been debated. Many regulators, citizens, and firms welcome them. Regulators faced with declining budgets are able to implement their mandates to enforce laws at lower costs. Citizens enjoy an increased supply of public goods [...]. Firms enjoy greater operational flexibility in designing and implementing their programs that rigid governmental regulations often deny them. Their relationship with regulators also becomes less adversarial. Thus, voluntary codes could channelize private interests toward achieving broader societal objectives in a manner from which both the regulators and the regulated parties benefit.

Many citizen and activist groups, however, view the codes as private regimes that are outside public scrutiny and that vest too much power with firms. This is not to say that these groups always favour government-sponsored regimes. The public-interest movement, in general, is suspicious of both the regulators and the firms [...]. [It] believes that regulators are amenable to “capture” (Stigler, 1971). Hence, they have faith in open and transparent administrative rule-making processes where public groups have statutory rights to provide input and to monitor decision-making processes. Many believe that voluntary codes do not provide such opportunities to citizen groups.” (p. 184)

Topalovic (2007) summarises the most important challenges of Responsible Care as follows:

⁹⁰ <http://www.responsiblecare.nl/responsible-care-duurzaamheid/responsible-care>

⁹¹ Aseem Prakash – Responsible Care: An Assessment (Business & Society 39(2): 183-209.

1. Self-reports of chemical firms are, in some cases, not standardized, accurate, or properly evaluated by an independent third party.
 2. Responsible Care compliance is not properly enforced and sanctions for noncompliance are not delivered.
 3. Firms are unaware of the business case for Responsible Care and the principles of sustainable development and industrial ecology.
 4. Responsible Care lacks proper incentives to motivate firms to comply with all the codes of conduct. This can lead to the use of the system for public relations purposes and greenwash.
 5. Communication issues within firms, between firms, and with the public hinder information gathering and dissemination, thereby hindering transparency.
 6. Chemical firms are not subject to the same set of standards if they are not part of an industry association.
 7. Actions of industry associations and chemical firms are not always harmonized with the principles of Responsible Care.
 8. Limitations of voluntary environmental programs and the possibility of a certain degree of legislation to compliment the voluntary initiatives are not given due consideration.
- (p.2)

The criticism levelled at the Responsible Care program was explained quite clearly in 2000 in a research article by Andrew King and Michael Lenox:

Responsible Care has operated up to now without explicit sanctions for malfeasance. As a result, our data suggest, it has fallen victim to enough opportunism that it includes a disproportionate number of poor performers, and its members do not improve faster than non-members. Thus, whatever the strength of the institutional forces that Responsible Care brings to bear on its members -and these forces appear considerable- they have not been enough to counteract opportunism. Since Responsible Care represents a leading example of self-regulation in the world, our findings highlight the difficulty of creating self-regulation without explicit sanctions.

This comparison leads us to hypothesize that explicit sanctions administered by informed outsiders may be needed to avoid opportunism within an industry self-regulatory scheme. Overseeing parties must be outsiders to ensure that sanctions are levied and are not used for other strategic purposes. Trade associations are limited as enforcers both legally and practically, since they are ultimately governed by their members. To prevent collusion, antitrust legislation forbids certain types of punitive actions on the part of trade associations. Industry members may fear that powerful association members may use sanctions strategically to punish weaker members and limit overall competition. (p. 713)

The national chemical associations have responded to this criticism in a variety of different ways. According to Topalovic (2007, p. 10-11), the American Chemistry Council (ACC) has made a 'hybrid Responsible Care/ISO 14001 environmental management system' mandatory. In Canada, the Canadian Chemical Producers' Association (CCPA) has appointed independent evaluation teams from the industry. Belanger (2009) writes:

"To counter the argument that RC is simply a public relations tactic, CCPA initiated two important activities. First is third party verification by a four-member team comprised of:

- Two experts in the implementation of Responsible Care. These are often people who have retired from the industry after being coordinators themselves.

- One expert in environmental matters. Often these have been professors of environmental science or environmentalists familiar with the development of Responsible Care.
- One representative of the community in which a company operates. This can be anyone with credibility in the community, for example a high school principal, or activist. The role of this individual is to confirm to the community that the process has indeed been a serious one.

The second activity in the results confirmation process is the production by each participant company of an annual report of all air, water and ground emissions, including waste and a five-year forecast.” (p. 22)

In contrast, the national chemical associations in Europe have been much less active in the implementation of external monitoring. Only the Chemical Industries Association in the United Kingdom has set hard emission targets since 2003.

Safe Chemicals Innovation Agenda

<https://www.chemischestoffengoeedgeregeld.nl/sites/default/files/39982%20-%20Safe%20Chemicals%20Innovation%20Agenda%20-%2020180613i6%20final%20copy.pdf>

The Safe Chemicals Innovation Agenda (SCIA) is a collaborative initiative of the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management and the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate. The SCIA identifies seven research priorities for safer chemical substances, materials, and products. These include alternatives for fluorinated chemicals in cleaning agents, less toxic flame retardants, and substitutes for volatile organic compounds in solvents.

Safer Chemicals Ingredients List

<https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice/safer-ingredients#scil>

The Safer Chemicals Ingredients List is a list of substances that meet the strict safety requirements of the Safer Choice programme of the EPA.

Safer Choice

<https://www.epa.gov/saferchoice>

The Safer Choice label is intended to make it easier for consumers to find products that are safer for people and the environment. Products with the Safer Choice label help consumers and commercial purchasers to identify products with safer chemical ingredients that are of the same quality and efficacy.

More than 2000 products have already received the Safer Choice label. The Safer Choice label is the successor to the Design for the Environment (DfE) label used by the EPA over the last 15 years for safer chemical products. The new label is the result of a year-long study carried out under producers, consumers, and other stakeholders in search of the best label.

Safer Made

<https://www.safermade.net/>

Safer Made is an investment fund that invests in safer products and technologies. The basic premise of the fund is that people prefer safer products. Safer Made works together with clothing brands and resellers who play a leading role in safety and sustainability. The technologies in which the fund invests enable brands and resellers to communicate a different story about safety and sustainability, which is attractive for consumers. Safer Made is an initiative of Adrian Horotan and Marty Mulvihill.

SIN List

<https://sinlist.chemsec.org/>

The European REACH regulations came into force in 2007. Within REACH, the most hazardous chemical substances were defined as Substances of Very High Concern, and these substances were placed on the Candidate List. The member states of the EU have agreed that the use of substances on this list must remain minimal. However, the regulation of substances within the framework of REACH has turned out to be a time-consuming process. Via the SIN list, ChemSec is attempting to accelerate this process.

The SIN List is a list of substances that according to ChemSec - based on the same criteria as those used in REACH - should be considered as chemical substances of very high concern:

1. CMR (Carcinogenic, Mutagenic, or Reprotoxic) substances;
2. PBT (Persistent, Bioaccumulative, and Toxic) substances;
3. 'Substances of an equivalent level of concern': sensitising, neurotoxic, and endocrine-disrupting substances.

The substances on the list are grouped according to their structural similarities. Practically all substances are placed in one of the 31 groups. Examples are bisphenols, phthalates, and perfluorinated compounds. The list was drafted by ChemSec in close collaboration with researchers and engineers, with input from an advisory committee consisting of leading European and American NGOs in the fields of the environment and health. The list is based on credible, publicly available information from existing databases and studies, as well as on new studies.

The European Commission has recognised the SIN List as an important driving force for innovation and, in its 2012 Global Chemicals Outlook, the United Nations Environmental Programme described the list as a useful risk assessment tool for chemical substances.

The list is used all over the world.

- Companies use the SIN List to identify substances as substances of very high concern before they are classified as such and placed on the Candidate List. This enables companies to launch the complex process of substitution in a timely manner.
- The SIN List serves many companies as a basis for the list of substances that are subject to limitations.
- Investors use the SIN List to avoid the financial risks of investing in companies using substances that might be banned in the future.
- The list is used in the *product stewardship* criterion of the Dow Jones Sustainability Index.
- Regulatory bodies in Europe, the US, and Asia use the list.
- NGOs use the SIN List to campaign for safer products and stricter regulations for chemical substances.

SINimilarity

<https://chemsec.org/business-tool/sinimilarity/about-sinimilarity>

SINimilarity is linked to the SIN List. It is a database that indicates whether a substance has structural similarities with a substance on the SIN List, which could point to similar problematic properties. The goal is to prevent the replacement of one problematic chemical substance by another problematic substance. The SINimilarity tool is based on data on more than 500,000 chemical structures. CAS or EC numbers are available for approximately 90,000 of these structures. It is therefore possible to carry out a search based on structure, name, or CAS/EC number in order to see whether the substance in question is similar to a substance on the SIN List. SINimilarity looks at the overall structural similarities with substances on the SIN List, as well as specific properties that could have an influence on the toxicity. If the substance in question does have this property, then the relevant group of substances on the SIN List is displayed.

SINimilarity gives an initial indication of the potential toxicity of a substance and is a reason to search for more information. In view of the structural similarities, have the potentially hazardous properties been adequately investigated? SINimilarity looks only at structural similarities. Further assessment is needed to determine the potential harmful effects. Substances that do not have any similarities with the substances on the SIN List can also be harmful.

Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management (SAICM)

<http://www.saicm.org/>

The *Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management* (SAICM) is a global and voluntary policy framework that aims to promote chemical safety. The basis for SAICM was laid down in 1992 at the UN Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro. In response to the recommendations from this conference,⁹² various international organisations established the *Inter-Organization Programme for the Sound Management of Chemicals (IOMC)*.⁹³ The IOMC introduced the 2020 SAICM goal at the 2002 World Summit in Johannesburg on sustainable development: implementing the responsible management of chemical substances during their life-cycle so that, in 2020, chemical substances would be produced and used in such a manner that the harmful effects for people and the environment are minimised.

SAICM was formally ratified during the First International Conference on the management of chemical products (ICCM1) on 6 February 2006 in Dubai, organised by the IOMC, UNEP and the *Intergovernmental Forum on Chemical Safety (IFCS)*.⁹⁴ At present, more than 10 international organisations participate in SAICM as well as over 90 NGOs and 175 countries. The programme is coordinated by an *Inter-Organization Coordinating Committee (IOCC)*, composed of representatives from the participating organisations. The IOCC guides, implements, and monitors the activities of participating organisations.

SAICM consists of three main components:

1. The *Dubai Declaration on International Chemicals Management*, which expresses the formal agreement at a high political level.
2. An overarching policy strategy that describes the scope, goals, financial considerations, underlying principles and approaches, and agreements with regard to the implementation and monitoring of SAICM.
3. A global action plan that supports the implementation of SAICM.

The *Dubai Declaration* states:

⁹² The recommendations of Chapter 19 of Agenda 21 target: 'Environmentally sound management of toxic chemicals, including prevention of illegal international traffic in toxic and dangerous products'. see: <https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/content/documents/Agenda21.pdf>

⁹³ The first Memorandum of Understanding from 1995 was signed by the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP), the International Labour Organisation (ILO), the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), the World Health Organisation (WHO), the United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO), and the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The United Nations Institute for Training and Research (UNITAR) followed in 1997, the World Bank in 2010, and the United Nations Development Programme in 2012. See: <https://www.who.int/iomc/participants/iomc-mou.pdf>

⁹⁴ The IFCS is a collaborative framework between governments, international and intergovernmental organisations and NGOs that is focused on the proper management of chemical substances. The IFCS was established in 1994: <https://www.who.int/ifcs/en/>. The present status of the forum is not completely clear. Although the websites are still up and running, they are quite outdated. It would seem that the last meeting was held in 2008: <https://www.who.int/ifcs/forums/six/en/>.

“The sound management of chemicals is essential if we are to achieve sustainable development ... Significant, but insufficient, progress has been made in international chemicals management ... The private sector has made considerable efforts to promote chemical safety through voluntary programmes and initiatives such as product stewardship and the chemicals industry’s Responsible Care programme. ... Non-governmental public health and environmental organizations, trade unions and other civil society organizations have made important contributions to the promotion of chemical safety. ... Progress in chemicals management has not, however, been sufficient globally and the environment worldwide continues to suffer from air, water and land contamination, impairing the health and welfare of millions. ... The need to take concerted action is accentuated by a wide range of chemical safety concerns at the international level, including a lack of capacity for managing chemicals in developing countries and countries with economies in transition. ... We commit ourselves in a spirit of solidarity and partnership to achieving chemical safety and thereby assisting in fighting poverty, protecting vulnerable groups and advancing public health and human security. ... We will promote the sound management of chemicals and hazardous waste as a priority in national, regional and international policy frameworks, including strategies for sustainable development, development assistance and poverty reduction.”⁹⁵

The overarching policy strategy explains the main goals, points of departure, and implementation mechanisms. The goals of SAICM can be grouped under five themes:

1. Risk reduction
2. Knowledge and information
3. Governance
4. Capacity building and technical collaboration
5. Illegal international trade

Organisation

The overarching policy strategy stipulates that an International Conference on Chemicals Management (ICCM) is to take place every three years. During these conferences, stakeholders meet each other to exchange information, discuss SAICM’s progress, and structure new activities. After ICCM1, three more international conferences were held: in Geneva (2009), Nairobi (2012) and again in Geneva (2015). ICCM5 is scheduled in 2020.

The international conferences are organised by the Conference Bureau. This bureau is composed of representatives from the participating organisations, four representatives of NGOs (since ICCM1, IPEN represents the NGOs, and ICCA the chemical industry) and the chair of the IOMC. The bureau receives support from the secretariat, which is based in Geneva at the Chemicals and Waste Section of the Economic Division of the United Nations Environmental Program.⁹⁶

⁹⁵http://www.saicm.org/Portals/12/Documents/saicmtexts/New%20SAICM%20Text%20with%20ICCM%20resolutions_E.pdf

⁹⁶<https://www.unenvironment.org/explore-topics/chemicals-waste>

In 2009, an *Open-ended Working Group (OEWG)* was also created. The OEWG focuses on implementing, developing, and improving SAICM by identifying and discussing emerging policy themes, devising new activities for the global action plan, and reviewing current initiatives and results of regional meetings. The OEWG is also facilitated by the secretariat. The OEWG held meetings in 2011 (Belgrade) and 2014 (Geneva). The next meeting is scheduled to take place from 2 to 4 April 2019 in Montevideo, where the agenda includes a discussion of the evaluation of SAICM and the preparation of recommendations for ICCM5.

Figure 3 - timeline of SAICM (2006 - 2015) - from the evaluation by Robert Nurick

During ICCM1, a *Quick Start Programme (QSP)* was also established - a financing programme that offers developing countries temporary financial support in preparing measures for the careful management of chemical substances. Since the start of the QSP programme, \$37 million has been invested in 184 projects in 108 different countries.

According to the recent independent evaluation of SAICM by Robert Nurick,⁹⁷ it was agreed during ICCM1 and 2 that the secretariat would have a staffing level of 6 to 7 fte but the staffing level was actually 3 to 4 fte.⁹⁸ The increased workload due to new initiatives (such as the creation of the OEWG, coordination of the *emerging policy issues* and preparation of the *overall orientation and guidance*) has not led to an increase in the staffing level of the secretariat.

All national governments are requested, via their Ministry of Foreign Affairs, to designate a *Strategic Approach National Focus Point*. These focal points would then represent all national departmental and interdepartmental agreements and stakeholder interests and serve all

⁹⁷ <http://www.saicm.org/Resources/SAICMStories/Draftindependentevaluation/tabid/6293/language/en-US/Default.aspx>

⁹⁸ See Nurick, p. 14

relevant areas.⁹⁹ In addition to these national focal points, the participating NGOs can designate NGO focal points, and the international organisations *can designate Intergovernmental Organizations focal points*. Finally, regional Strategic Approach focal points can be designated to simplify the organisation of regional meetings.

The national NGOs play an important role in implementing SAICM via national campaigns for regulating hazardous substances in consumer products, agriculture, and waste processing.¹⁰⁰ The chemical industry plays an important role in implementing SAICM by implementing the Responsible Care programme and the *Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals (GHS)*.¹⁰¹

Figure 1: SAICM Institutional structure and stakeholders (2006-2015)

Figure 4 - SAICM structure and stakeholders - from the evaluation by Robert Nurick

SAICM is funded via contributions from governments and participating organisations. According to the website, the donors who have contributed to the programme since the ICCM3 in 2012 include national governments (among them Austria, Belgium, Benin, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Guyana, Kenya, Norway, Pakistan, Slovenia, Sweden, Switzerland, the US, and the Netherlands), the European Union, the United Nations Environmental Programme, and the *International Council of Chemical Associations (ICCA)*.¹⁰²

However, according to the evaluation by Robert Nurick, the available budgets over the period 2006-2015 remained far below the targeted budgets. In 2013, 2014, and 2015, UNEP contributed nearly extra half a million dollars extra in order to prevent a crisis.

⁹⁹ According to the SAICM website, Reginald Hernaus (Infrastructure and Environment) is the Dutch focal point.

¹⁰⁰ see Nurick, p. 12

¹⁰¹ https://www.chemsafetypro.com/Topics/GHS/global_ghs_implementation.html

¹⁰² <http://www.saicm.org/About/Donors/tabid/5512/language/en-US/Default.aspx>

Over the period 2006-2015, the Netherlands provided a voluntary contribution of over \$260,000, or 2% of the total voluntary contributions. In addition, the Netherlands contributed almost \$700,000 (also 2% of the total) to the Quick Start Programme fund.

Over the same period, ICCA voluntarily contributed almost \$300,000 (3% of the budget).

The European Commission made the biggest contribution: 2.6 million dollars (23%) to the voluntary contributions and 11 million (28%) to the QSP fund. Major contributions were also made by the United States, Sweden, and Norway.

Implementation

Over the years, resolutions were formulated within SAICM targeting eight policy priorities:

1. Lead in paint
2. Chemicals in products
3. Hazardous substance within the life cycle of electrical and electronic products
4. Nanotechnology and manufactured nanomaterials
5. Endocrine-disrupting chemicals
6. Environmentally persistent pharmaceutical pollutants
7. Perfluorinated chemicals and the transition to safer alternatives
8. Highly hazardous pesticides

One of the ways that the progress being made in the implementation of SAICM is measured is via the *SAICM progress reports*. There are 20 indicators for measuring progress on each of the 5 goals. Each of these indicators measures the increase in the number of countries that indicate that they have implemented policy mechanisms for the topic concerned: for example, the number of countries that implement management strategies for chemical substances (risk reduction) or the number of countries that have coordination mechanisms in place for multi-stakeholder consultation (governance).¹⁰³ In 2012, a base level report was published for the period 2006-2008. After that, progress reports were published for the periods 2009-2010 and 2011-2013. Data is presently being collected for the period 2014-2016.

During ICCM 4, an *Overall Orientation and Guidance for Achieving the 2020 Goal* was adopted, a voluntary instrument that designates six core activities for achieving the 2020 goal:

1. Enhance the responsibility of stakeholders
2. Establish and strengthen national legislative and regulatory frameworks for chemicals and waste
3. Mainstream the sound management of chemicals and waste in the sustainable development agenda
4. Increase risk reduction and information sharing efforts on emerging policy issues
5. Promote information access
6. Assess progress towards the 2020 goal of minimizing the adverse effects of chemicals on human health and the environment.

¹⁰³ <http://www.saicm.org/Portals/12/Documents/SAICM-List%20of%20indicators%20for%20reporting%20progress.pdf>

The Guidance also identifies 11 basic elements that are crucial for achieving the 2020 goal:

1. Legal frameworks that address the life cycle of chemicals and waste
2. Relevant enforcement and compliance mechanisms
3. Implementation of chemicals and waste-related multilateral environmental agreements, as well as health, labour and other relevant conventions and voluntary mechanisms
4. Strong institutional frameworks and coordination mechanisms among relevant stakeholders
5. Collection and systems for the transparent sharing of relevant data and information among all relevant stakeholders using a life cycle approach, such as the implementation of the Globally Harmonized System of Classification and Labelling of Chemicals
6. Industry participation and defined responsibility across the life cycle, including cost recovery policies and systems as well as the incorporation of sound chemicals management into corporate policies and practices
7. Inclusion of the sound management of chemicals and waste in national health, labour, social, environment and economic budgeting processes and development plans
8. Chemicals risk assessment and risk reduction through the use of best practices
9. Strengthened capacity to deal with chemicals accidents, including institutional strengthening for poison centres
10. Monitoring and assessing the impacts of chemicals on health and the environment
11. Development and promotion of environmentally sound and safer alternatives

Independent evaluation

In the period 2016-2018, an independent evaluation of SAICM was carried out by Robert Nurick of the University of Sussex. An online questionnaire distributed to the SAICM stakeholders (112 respondents) with regard to the overarching policy goals of SAICM shows a mixed picture. Just over three quarters of the respondents think that progress has been made on the topic of 'sharing knowledge and information'. The OECD eChem portal and the REACH portal are named as examples in this regard. 71% thinks that progress has been made on the topic of 'risk reduction'. Slightly less than 20% think that no progress has been made on this topic. Among the non-governmental participants, the industrial sector has a more positive opinion regarding progress on this topic than does the civil society sector. Only one out of three participants thinks that progress has been made on the topic of 'illegal international trade'.

More than half of the respondents think that progress has been made with regard to the emerging policy issue of 'chemicals in products'. Industrial parties, who were very actively involved in this workgroup, referred to a variety of initiatives by the industry in this area. However, NGOs expressed their concerns regarding the lack of transparency due to the confidentiality of industrial information and the voluntary nature of participation.

Only 32% of the respondents found that progress has been made on the policy issue of 'hazardous substances in electrical products'. That percentage was 37% for 'nanotechnology', 38% for the transition to alternatives for perfluorinated compounds, and 48% for 'very harmful pesticides'.

An internal evaluation by the SAICM secretariat in 2014 of the progress made with regard to the 2020 goals concluded that these goals are not likely to be achieved in 2020. In Africa, the 2010-2014 period was even characterised by a regression.

In summary, Nurick states that the power of SAICM lies in the ambition to work together to achieve a broadly supported policy framework for the responsible management of chemical substances – a voluntarily global initiative. SAICM provided a platform for governmental and non-governmental parties from various sectors to discuss the appropriate management of chemical substances in an atmosphere of mutual trust and collaboration. SAICM's structure also gave non-governmental organisations a role in the decision-making process.

Actions were identified and implemented on the topic of emerging policy issues. Progress was achieved in particular on the topic 'lead in paint': under the leadership of UNEP and WHO, several governments imposed legal restrictions on the use of lead in paint.

However, Nurick also identifies weaknesses in the programme. He emphasises capacity shortage as a major cause of these weaknesses. For example, due to understaffing, the secretariat was not able to create an information clearinghouse. In addition, as it turned out, the model based on a focal point per country (often consisting of a single co-worker at the Ministry of the Environment or sometimes Agriculture or Foreign Affairs) made it impossible to effectively share and communicate knowledge at the national level.

The capacity of the QSP programme was also insufficient to satisfy the global need for support in establishing management programmes in less wealthy countries. Also, insufficient progress was made in the area of illegal trade: illegal pesticides, trade in mercury, dumping of e-waste, and smuggling of banned chemicals. Finally, an analysis of the progress report showed that the gap between developed countries and developing countries seems to increase instead of decrease with the implementation of SAICM.

SUBSPORT – Substitution Support Portal

<http://www.subsportplus.eu/about-the-portal>

The SUBSPORT web portal aims to simplify the substitution of hazardous substances. SUBSPORT is a free multilanguage platform for exchanging information on alternative substances and technologies. The platform offers various instruments and manuals for the assessment of substances and substitution. SUBSPORT aims to be the first point of departure for everyone who is interested in the replacement of hazardous substances. SUBSPORT can help companies to comply with European regulations on substitution requirements, and also

serves as a source of information for other stakeholders such as authorities, environmental and consumer organisations, and scientific institutions.

Textile Guide

<https://chemsec.org/business-tool/textile-guide/>

The Textile Guide is an initiative of ChemSec, The International Chemical Secretariat, based in Sweden (for more information, look under Marketplace). The Textile Guide explains the process of managing substances from the perspective of the textile industry. This manual is a starting point for small and medium-sized textile companies in managing the substances in their processes and products. The Textile Guide shows where problematic substances are used and how they can be phased out.

Chemical substances are used in every phase of the textile production process, and some of these substances are hazardous. Hazardous substances pose a threat to human health and the environment. They can also damage the reputation of the brand. The regulations that apply to chemical substances are becoming stricter all over the world: increasing numbers of hazardous substances must meet regulatory requirements. The Textile Guide helps companies to avoid these substances in three steps:

1. *Identify the chemical substances in the production chain.* This is the first step on the path to a product that is free of hazardous substances, and it requires research into the production history of the product. Which substances were used in the production process, and which substances are present in the end product?
2. *Evaluate the chemical substances in the production chain.* Substantial quantities of chemical substances are needed for the production of textiles. Some of these pose a hazard to people and the environment.
3. *Do something with the chemical substances in the production chain.* If substances of concern are used in the production, it's important to identify the potential opportunities for avoiding the use of these substances.

The Chemical Footprint Project

The Chemical Footprint Project is an initiative of Clean Production Action. The project creates a benchmark for companies regarding the use of chemical substances of concern and the selection of safer alternatives. Companies first fill out a questionnaire with 19 questions on four topics:

1. Management strategy: company policy on management of chemical substances;
2. Chemical inventory: the information collected by the company on chemical substances in products and in the value chain;
3. Footprint measurement: the data available to the company on the use of substances of very high concern and the progress made in the area of safer alternatives;

4. Public disclosure of data and verification: the degree to which the company discloses data on chemical substances.

Taken together, the questions represent a score of 100 points. By determining their score, companies obtain an indication of how their policy on substances compares to that of other participating companies.

The Massachusetts Toxics Use Reduction Institute (TURI)

<https://www.turi.org/>

The Massachusetts Toxics Use Reduction Institute (TURI) is an institution run by the State of Massachusetts in the USA. TURI was established in 1989 pursuant to the Toxics Use Reduction Act. TURI is based at the University of Massachusetts in Lowell. TURI offers information, manuals, and instruments for achieving a safer and more sustainable living and working environment in Massachusetts.

Tox21

<https://tox21.gov/>

The Toxicology in the 21st Century (Tox21) Consortium is a federal collaborative framework participated in by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), the National Toxicology Program (NTP) of the National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS), the National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS), and the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in the United States.

In the course of their lives, people are exposed to thousands of chemical substances that are present in food, cleaning agents, medicines, and the environment. Researchers actually know little about the potential harmful effects of most of these substances, such as their toxicity. Over 30% of promising new medicines fail to pass human clinical trials as they turn out to be toxic, in spite of promising preclinical studies in animal experiments. New methods for determining chemical toxicity can help in the assessment of substances present in the environment and the development of new medicines.

There are several challenges facing the traditional assessment of the toxicity of industrial chemical substances, pesticides, foodstuffs, and medicines. These challenges include the number of substances that have to be tested, the time and resources needed to carry out the tests, and the unexpected effects that can occur in spite of extensive toxicological research in clinical trials.

For that reason, the Tox 21 Consortium was established in 2008. The consortium aims to encourage the further development of toxicology in the 21st century via the development of fast and efficient measurement methods for testing the safety of commercial chemicals, pesticides, foodstuffs, and medical products. Since the start of the programme, Tox21 has

developed and validated more than 70 cell-based in vitro tests that make use of quantitative high-throughput screening.

ToxCast

<https://www.epa.gov/chemical-research/toxicity-forecasting>

The United States EPA needs fast and efficient measurement methods in order to be able to evaluate and prioritise thousands of chemical substances. The EPA's Toxicity Forecaster (ToxCast) generates data and predictive models for approximately 1800 chemical substances, ranging from ingredients in industrial and consumer products to food additives and potential "green" chemicals that could offer a safer alternative to existing substances. ToxCast uses high-throughput screening methods and computational toxicology to organise and prioritise substances. ToxCast screens substances in more than 700 high-throughput tests that measure a broad range of cell reactions. ToxCast data represent one of the contributions by the EPA to the Tox21 initiative. All ToxCast data are publicly available.

TSCA Chemical Substance Inventory

<https://www.epa.gov/tsca-inventory>

The Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) Chemical Substance Inventory contains all chemical substances that are produced, processed, or imported in the United States and that are not covered by a TSCA exemption. Section 8 (b) of the Toxic Substances Control Act (TSCA) requires the EPA to maintain and publish a list of all chemical substances that are made, processed, or imported in the United States. Within that context, the TSCA Inventory, also referred to simply as the 'Inventory', plays a crucial role in the regulations that apply to most of the industrial chemical substances in the US.

The Inventory was first published in 1979 and contained the chemical substances that were being commercially traded since January 1975. A second version of the list, containing approximately 62,000 chemical substances, was published in 1982. The TSCA Inventory has by now grown to include approximately 85,000 substances. The EPA offers free access to the Inventory.

As part of EPA's commitment to strengthen the management of chemicals and increase information on chemicals, the Agency provides free access to the Inventory online. The Inventory contains organic and inorganic compounds and polymers, as well as so-called UVCBs: chemical substances of unknown or variable composition, complex reaction products and biological materials. Substances that are not subject to the TSCA regulations are not included in the list. The use of these substances is subject to other regulatory frameworks such as regulations for pesticides, foodstuffs, medicines, cosmetics, tobacco, nuclear materials, or munition.

If a substance is included in the Inventory, then it is considered to be an 'existing' chemical substance under the TSCA regulations. Every substance that is not included in the list is considered to be a 'new chemical substance'. Besides serving to define whether a substance is a 'new' or 'existing' substance, the list contains 'flags' for those existing substances that are subject to restrictions with regard to their production or use. Determining whether a substance is listed in the Inventory is a crucial step prior to the production or import of a substance. Section 5 of the TSCA requires every party that intends to produce a new chemical substance for commercial purposes not covered by an exemption to submit a Premanufacture Notice (PMN) to the EPA no later than 90 days before the start of the activity.